

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30004630

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -5.04 MAX_MED: -2.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30004535

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.123 MAX_MED: 2.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethomorph
 CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22
 M4ID: 30004643

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.79 MAX_MED: 1.52 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tebufenozide
 CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03
 M4ID: 30004806

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0546 MAX_MED: 0.305 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30005186

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.11 MAX_MED: 2.66 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: DMSO.POS (spid not in DB)

CHID: NA CASRN: NA

SPID(S): DMSO.POS

M4ID: 30005241

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.189 MAX_MED: 0 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30004638

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.74 MAX_MED: -1.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30005090

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.163 MAX_MED: -0.548 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Atrazine

CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11

M4ID: 30004534

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.6 MAX_MED: -1.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30004774

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.12 MAX_MED: 3.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30004579

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.773 MAX_MED: -0.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30004764

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.93 MAX_MED: 3.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30005146

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30004998

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0505 MAX_MED: 0.0475 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butylparaben

CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17

M4ID: 30004816

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 3.68 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30004533

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.57 MAX_MED: 0.554 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30005212

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.57 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30005112

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.714 MAX_MED: 1.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30004674

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.4 MAX_MED: 1.97 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30005050

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.6 MAX_MED: -1.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30004596

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.91 MAX_MED: 3.39 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene
CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014
M4ID: 30004507

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.482 MAX_MED: -1.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30005204

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	98.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 1.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester

CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13

M4ID: 30005060

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.376 MAX_MED: -0.085 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30004771

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.24 MAX_MED: 1.99 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
 CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
 M4ID: 30004665

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.342 MAX_MED: 1.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline
 CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08
 M4ID: 30005137

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.7 MAX_MED: 3.16 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30004591

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.47 MAX_MED: 0.291 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30004675

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.427 MAX_MED: 0.234 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30004663

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.61	MAX_MED:	1.93	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30004705

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.57 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30004805

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 4.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: dl-Menthol
 CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14
 M4ID: 30005035

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.657 MAX_MED: -0.831 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil

CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19

M4ID: 30005102

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.07 MAX_MED: 3.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30004567

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.55 MAX_MED: 1.25 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30004732

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	97.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.03 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline
 CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18
 M4ID: 30004695

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 3.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30004738

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.816 MAX_MED: 0.701 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid
 CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03
 M4ID: 30004662

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.07 MAX_MED: -0.0457 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin

CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02

M4ID: 30004687

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.51 MAX_MED: 2.85 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
M4ID: 30004627

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.553	MAX_MED:	-0.331	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30004495

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.33 MAX_MED: 2.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30004743

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.27 MAX_MED: 2.54 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30005062

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.76 MAX_MED: 1.77 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiourea
 CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17
 M4ID: 30004576

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.43 MAX_MED: 4.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: dl-alpha-Tocopheryl acetate

CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08

M4ID: 30005161

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.2 MAX_MED: 4.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene

CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08

M4ID: 30004657 BRK

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	22.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 23.8 MAX_MED: 0.669 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate

CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18

M4ID: 30004719

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.8 MAX_MED: 2.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Urethane

CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11

M4ID: 30004558

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.81 MAX_MED: -1.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30005105

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.39 MAX_MED: 2.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nonanoic acid

CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21

M4ID: 30004932

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.841 MAX_MED: -0.412 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid

CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07

M4ID: 30004610

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.81 MAX_MED: -1.09 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30004655

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.316 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30004543

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	111.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.42 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline

CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22

M4ID: 30004571

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.47 MAX_MED: 1.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30004668

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.237 MAX_MED: 0.0421 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime
CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10
M4ID: 30004559

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.25	MAX_MED:	1.99	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate
CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20
M4ID: 30004717

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	121.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.92	MAX_MED:	1.3	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30004561

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.289 MAX_MED: 0.655 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30004718

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.426 MAX_MED: 0.0826 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol
 CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04
 M4ID: 30005093

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.53	MAX_MED: 3.8	BMAD: 1.48
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COFF: 14.8	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile

CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14

M4ID: 30004555

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.553 MAX_MED: -0.715 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30005100

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	119.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30005027

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.53 MAX_MED: 2.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30004950

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.726 MAX_MED: 0.779 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate

CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01

M4ID: 30004616

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.55 MAX_MED: -1.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30005052

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.239 MAX_MED: 0.489 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Nonanol
 CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22
 M4ID: 30004931

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.68 MAX_MED: 2.77 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30004703

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.06	MAX_MED:	1.82	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22

M4ID: 30004787

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.75 MAX_MED: 4.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene

CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24

M4ID: 30005049

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.704 MAX_MED: 0.515 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30005047

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.44 MAX_MED: 2.15 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30004788

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	108.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.66 MAX_MED: 2.24 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30004516

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.919 MAX_MED: 1.29 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid

CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01

M4ID: 30005216

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.89 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Lactose

CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01

M4ID: 30004952

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.213 MAX_MED: -0.00172 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30004595

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.92 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30004735

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	100.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.06 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30004712

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00481 MAX_MED: -0.423 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30005059

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.846 MAX_MED: 1.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30004658

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.58 MAX_MED: -0.553 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetracycline

CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11

M4ID: 30005182

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.76 MAX_MED: 3.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30005174

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.85 MAX_MED: 2.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30004904

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0883 MAX_MED: -0.215 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Clofentezine
 CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05
 M4ID: 30004564

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.52 MAX_MED: 2.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30004733

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.83 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene
 CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23
 M4ID: 30004642

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.657 MAX_MED: -0.657 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30005113

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.13 MAX_MED: 0.743 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30004514

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.88 MAX_MED: -1.98 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfate

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30004782

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.27 MAX_MED: 2.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethylamine
 CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05
 M4ID: 30004636

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.2 MAX_MED: -1.16 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30004664

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.372 MAX_MED: 0.0661 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30004789

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.79 MAX_MED: 4.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: MCPB
 CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13
 M4ID: 30004604

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.242 MAX_MED: 0.185 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30004709

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.426 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phosphoric acid
 CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14
 M4ID: 30004603

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.03 MAX_MED: 1.99 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexythiazox
 CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24
 M4ID: 30004641

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.33 MAX_MED: 3.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30004565

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.815 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30004785

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.19 MAX_MED: 4.08 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl

CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19

M4ID: 30005030

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.09 MAX_MED: 3.13 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30004639

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.55 MAX_MED: 0.431 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid

CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13

M4ID: 30005180

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30005094

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0946 MAX_MED: 0.307 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30004756

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	114.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.99 MAX_MED: 2.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30005083

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.582 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide

CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23

M4ID: 30004714

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.511 MAX_MED: -0.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30004780

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.48 MAX_MED: 3.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene
 CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04
 M4ID: 30005141

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.31 MAX_MED: 4.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30005025

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.35	MAX_MED:	3.1	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30004926

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.787 MAX_MED: -0.365 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30005000

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.55 MAX_MED: 1.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30005003

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.1 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30004592

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.44 MAX_MED: 1.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea
 CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12
 M4ID: 30004557

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	202.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.81 MAX_MED: -0.115 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30004997

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.828 MAX_MED: 0.599 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30005023

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.402 MAX_MED: 0.572 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane

CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23

M4ID: 30004522

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.82 MAX_MED: -0.619 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30004693

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.783 MAX_MED: -0.646 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30004713

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.65 MAX_MED: 1.98 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride

CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10

M4ID: 30005063

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.09 MAX_MED: 0.495 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30005074

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.09 MAX_MED: -1.09 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
 CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
 M4ID: 30004685

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.519 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30004650

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.59 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30004934

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.877 MAX_MED: -1.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30004745

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	115.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.76 MAX_MED: 2.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30004848

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.53 MAX_MED: 3.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30005168

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 1.33 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30005046

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.63 MAX_MED: -1.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30004568

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	121.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0714 MAX_MED: -0.0626 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride

CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16

M4ID: 30005081

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.714 MAX_MED: -0.0647 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30005170

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.26 MAX_MED: 3.74 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30004820

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.68 MAX_MED: 3.77 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30004584

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.545	MAX_MED:	0.758	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30004979

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.53 MAX_MED: 2.98 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30005166

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	121.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.42 MAX_MED: 2.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol
 CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19
 M4ID: 30005054

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.678 MAX_MED: 0.494 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30004949

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.04 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl decanoate

CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21

M4ID: 30004476

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.422 MAX_MED: -0.317 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30004620

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.662 MAX_MED: -0.701 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedio1 diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30004527

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0958 MAX_MED: 0.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30004698

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.43 MAX_MED: 1.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23

M4ID: 30005194

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.51 MAX_MED: 3.66 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30004730

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.05 MAX_MED: 4.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate

CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24

M4ID: 30004689

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.3 MAX_MED: 1.13 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30004699

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline

CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001

M4ID: 30004520

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30005118

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30005002

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.58 MAX_MED: -0.737 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30004765

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 2.33 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol
CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20
M4ID: 30004669

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.905 MAX_MED: -1.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30004826

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.44 MAX_MED: 3.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylacetoacetamide

CHID: 27454 CASRN: 2044-64-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L05

M4ID: 30004588

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.181 MAX_MED: -0.407 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiocarbazide
 CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20
 M4ID: 30004645

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.14 MAX_MED: -1.73 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide

CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09

M4ID: 30004680

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.554 MAX_MED: 0.116 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrifluoride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30004496

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.297 MAX_MED: 0.549 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30004575

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.267 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30004475

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30004700

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.5 MAX_MED: -1.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid
 CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07
 M4ID: 30004682

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.19 MAX_MED: 0.161 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30005098

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.227 MAX_MED: 0.471 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlormid

CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11

M4ID: 30005158

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.96 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol

CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13

M4ID: 30005108

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.03 MAX_MED: 3.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30004901

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.47 MAX_MED: 0.893 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal

CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24

M4ID: 30005001

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.5 MAX_MED: 3.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30004754

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.4 MAX_MED: 2.92 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30004781

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.38 MAX_MED: 1.43 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30004513

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 2.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate

CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02

M4ID: 30005167

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.18 MAX_MED: 4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30004623

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.306 MAX_MED: 0.758 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30005006

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.84 MAX_MED: 0.909 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30004545

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.814 MAX_MED: 1.47 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30004786

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	118.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.64 MAX_MED: 1.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium persulfate
 CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07
 M4ID: 30004562

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.6 MAX_MED: -0.293 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether

CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15

M4ID: 30005034

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0412 MAX_MED: 0.0354 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02

M4ID: 30004759

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.56 MAX_MED: 3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30005095

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.47 MAX_MED: 3.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
M4ID: 30004711

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	121.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.34 MAX_MED: 1.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30004956

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30004690

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	125.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.839 MAX_MED: -0.839 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30004612

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.22 MAX_MED: 4.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30005097

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.49 MAX_MED: 3.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30005230

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	86.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.31 MAX_MED: 4.31 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pymetrozine
 CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20
 M4ID: 30005029

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.582 MAX_MED: -0.258 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30004607

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.23	MAX_MED:	1.09	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetramethrin
 CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004
 M4ID: 30004517

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.97	MAX_MED: 3.57	BMAD: 1.48
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COFF: 14.8	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30005064

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.33 MAX_MED: 2.33 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
M4ID: 30004473

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.63 MAX_MED: 3.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30004537

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.531 MAX_MED: 1.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide

CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19

M4ID: 30004766

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.54 MAX_MED: 3.15 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butachlor
 CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11
 M4ID: 30004486

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.963 MAX_MED: 0.731 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30004648

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.642 MAX_MED: -1.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Imazamox

CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07

M4ID: 30004634

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.81	MAX_MED:	-0.545	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30004497

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.92	MAX_MED:	3.21	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30004784

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.188 MAX_MED: 0.646 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Monocrotophos
 CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009
 M4ID: 30004512

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.27 MAX_MED: -0.485 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30004720

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.86 MAX_MED: 2.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl

CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09

M4ID: 30004728

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 3.15 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Chloridazon

CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04

M4ID: 30004757

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 4.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30005096

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.69 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fosthiazate

CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022

M4ID: 30004499

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.74 MAX_MED: 2.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30004840

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.83 MAX_MED: 3.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tralkoxydim
 CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10
 M4ID: 30004583

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.249 MAX_MED: 1.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30004768

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.22 MAX_MED: 2.24 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30005155

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.74 MAX_MED: 2.58 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Codlure

CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01

M4ID: 30005048

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 1.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30004593

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	130.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.99 MAX_MED: 3.37 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30004725

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30004797

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.21 MAX_MED: 3.26 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30004758

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	113.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.92 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30004519

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	119.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.21 MAX_MED: 2.68 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30005088

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.81	MAX_MED:	1.72	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30004677

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.82 MAX_MED: 0.264 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30005214

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.62 MAX_MED: 2.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30005071

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 2.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl
 CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13
 M4ID: 30004676

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0243 MAX_MED: 0.234 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane

CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16

M4ID: 30004769

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.72 MAX_MED: 2.86 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium iodide
 CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12
 M4ID: 30004581

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.38 MAX_MED: 0.471 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30004701

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.962	MAX_MED:	0.754	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30004538

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.43 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol

CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012

M4ID: 30004509

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.216 MAX_MED: 2.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30005192

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.74 MAX_MED: 3.97 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30005177

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 2.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: R-(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30004749

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.16 MAX_MED: 1.91 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30005110

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.29 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30005122

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	120.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.01 MAX_MED: 1.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30004802

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.06 MAX_MED: 2.08 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30005077

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30005131

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.809 MAX_MED: 1.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile

CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07

M4ID: 30004706

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.58 MAX_MED: 4.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30005116

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	119.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.84 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30004723

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	113.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.71 MAX_MED: 2.24 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Citronellal

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30005190

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.59 MAX_MED: 3.94 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate
CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03
M4ID: 30005142

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.72	MAX_MED:	3.01	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine
CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19
M4ID: 30004742

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.86 MAX_MED: 2.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30004500

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.16 MAX_MED: -0.569 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate
 CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11
 M4ID: 30004582

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.28 MAX_MED: 3.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)

CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12

M4ID: 30005133

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.74 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea

CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12

M4ID: 30004773

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.56	MAX_MED:	1.61	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine

CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010

M4ID: 30004511

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.35 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propylbenzene

CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11

M4ID: 30005206

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.74	MAX_MED:	4.03	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane

CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12

M4ID: 30004653

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.977 MAX_MED: -0.256 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30004747

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	110.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.82 MAX_MED: 3.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30004783

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	111.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.45 MAX_MED: 2.41 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30004716

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	97.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.12 MAX_MED: 1.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30004586

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.88 MAX_MED: -0.923 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30004678

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.36	MAX_MED:	1.08	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30004508

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.53 MAX_MED: -0.972 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30005119

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.63 MAX_MED: 2.73 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30004724

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	113.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.373 MAX_MED: -0.428 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30004915

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.98 MAX_MED: 0.773 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30005143

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.71 MAX_MED: 3.26 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30005024

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.962 MAX_MED: 0.859 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30004928

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.481 MAX_MED: -0.523 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30004976

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.609 MAX_MED: 0.342 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: PHA-00543613
 CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01
 M4ID: 30004688

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.212 MAX_MED: -1.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30004556

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.61 MAX_MED: -1.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30004640

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.752 MAX_MED: -0.00841 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30004951

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.585 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30004536

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.57 MAX_MED: 0.546 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30005188

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.48 MAX_MED: 2.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30004484

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.98 MAX_MED: -0.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30004999

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.13 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30004552

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.711 MAX_MED: 1.97 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30004844

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.95 MAX_MED: 4.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30004608

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.883 MAX_MED: 0.925 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate
 CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03
 M4ID: 30004590

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 1.87 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolid

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30004628

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.78 MAX_MED: -1.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30004975

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.02 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30004651

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.459 MAX_MED: 0.108 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30005179

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	110.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.06 MAX_MED: 3.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone
 CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014
 M4ID: 30004891

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0751 MAX_MED: -0.271 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30005082

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.64 MAX_MED: 2.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30004795

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	125.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.57 MAX_MED: 4.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30004925

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.6 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507

CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13

M4ID: 30004652

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.05 MAX_MED: 0.972 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30004860

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.16 MAX_MED: -0.369 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30004870

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.4 MAX_MED: -2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Amitrole
 CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020
 M4ID: 30004885

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.332 MAX_MED: -0.283 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride
 CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10
 M4ID: 30004967

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.9e-10	-0.935	1.35
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.29	-2.75	1.54	-2.3	6.36
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.4	173.4	177.26
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.57	3.57	3.56

MAX_MEAN: 0.672 MAX_MED: 0.851 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Aspartame

CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12

M4ID: 30004605

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.26 MAX_MED: -0.469 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride

CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09

M4ID: 30005016

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.9 MAX_MED: -3.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30004990

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1 MAX_MED: -1.47 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzoic acid
 CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12
 M4ID: 30005085

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.18e-11	-0.528	1.49
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.73e-09	-0.409	1.24	-0.051	5.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.53	155.53	159.53
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	2.88	2.88	2.88

MAX_MEAN: 1.31 MAX_MED: 0.744 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole
CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21
M4ID: 30004908

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.933 MAX_MED: -0.939 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol

CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07

M4ID: 30004922

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.05 MAX_MED: -3.39 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate
 CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16
 M4ID: 30004481

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.68e-12 -0.627 1.17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.76e-09 -0.46 0.859 -0.194 5.2
 sd: 1.35e-05 12500 17900 5530 148000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.74	188.74	192.74
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.64	4.64	4.64

MAX_MEAN: -0.215 MAX_MED: 0.392 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone

CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21

M4ID: 30005172

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 31.6 MAX_MED: 31.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Caffeine
 CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18
 M4ID: 30004983

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.14 MAX_MED: -1.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Monuron
 CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12
 M4ID: 30005013

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.38e-10 -0.924 0.496
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.09e-07 -2.14 2.53 -1.39 6.53
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.73	171.73	175.73
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.57	3.57	3.57

MAX_MEAN: 0.754 MAX_MED: 0.675 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30005032

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.27 MAX_MED: -2.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
 CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
 M4ID: 30005069

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.57 2.8 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.68e-08 0.159 7.94 0.419 7.02
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.6	209.6	213.6
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.69	6.69	6.69

MAX_MEAN: 4.4 MAX_MED: 4.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30004989

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.14e-10	-1.11	1.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.91e-08	-1.64	1.2	-1.36	7.06
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.51	177.51	181.51
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.92	3.92	3.92

MAX_MEAN: -0.765 MAX_MED: 0.359 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlone
 CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09
 M4ID: 30005136

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.69e-10 1.86 1.42
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.79 0.894 8 1.92 18
 sd: 1.26 0.595 31.9 0.0868 29.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.1	183.1	184.34
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	4.9	4.9	4.79

MAX_MEAN: 2.51 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30004622

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.08 MAX_MED: -1.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30004549

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.29 MAX_MED: -2.39 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene
 CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06
 M4ID: 30005019 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.5	0.288	8
sd:	2.84	1.45	38.4

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.07	-0.506	7.88	-0.254	17.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	271.4	276.34	281.4
PROB:	0.92	0.08	0.01
RMSE:	28.68	27.64	28.68

MAX_MEAN: 43.7 MAX_MED: 53.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS: 8; 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide
 CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006
 M4ID: 30004899

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.56e-12 -0.128 1.36
 sd: 4.91e-05 18200 121000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.02e-09 -0.496 1.77 -0.114 5.35
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.25	181.25	185.25
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.11	4.11	4.11

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 1.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30004884

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.717 MAX_MED: -0.0107 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluometuron
 CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012
 M4ID: 30004893

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.932 MAX_MED: -0.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30005176 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	275.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	24.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 54.4 MAX_MED: 53.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8; 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30004909

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.86 MAX_MED: -0.199 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3

CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22

M4ID: 30004907

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.6	2.8	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.84e-08	2.24	6.33	2.51	0.454
sd:	0.000597	1600	85700	6630	13300

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.84	218.85	222.84
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.58	7.58	7.58

MAX_MEAN: 4.3 MAX_MED: 4.09 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30005031

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.59 MAX_MED: -2.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30004731

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.28 MAX_MED: 4.72 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline
 CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06
 M4ID: 30004539

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.59e-09	2.77	1.05
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.07	1.35	8	1.65	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.27	170.27	173.41
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.6	3.6	3.57

MAX_MEAN: 1.4 MAX_MED: 1.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate
 CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15
 M4ID: 30004530

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.67 MAX_MED: -3.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30004865

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	248.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.83 MAX_MED: -0.885 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Busulfan
 CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15
 M4ID: 30004482

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.47 MAX_MED: -2.53 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30005015

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.46e-11	1.22	1.19
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.75e-09	1.09	2.45	1.45	5.28
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.87	186.87	190.87
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.51	4.51	4.51

MAX_MEAN: 0.871 MAX_MED: 0.673 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30005038

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3e-10	0.485	1.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.24e-10	-0.0149	1.73	0.423	6.03
sd:	0.000664	54100	134000	66800	4380000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.3	171.3	175.3
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.62	3.62	3.62

MAX_MEAN: 0.823 MAX_MED: 1.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrofurazone
 CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005
 M4ID: 30004900

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.16 MAX_MED: -2.43 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30004868

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.848 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine
 CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21
 M4ID: 30005220

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	15.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 38 MAX_MED: 38.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate

CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09

M4ID: 30004752 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.03e-08	2.77	1.36
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.26e-10	1.98	1.59	2.68	5.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	232.32	238.32	242.32
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.89	10.89	10.89

MAX_MEAN: 1.08 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Rifampicin

CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17

M4ID: 30004480

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.72 MAX_MED: -1.37 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sulfasalazine

CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05

M4ID: 30004948

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0198 MAX_MED: -0.033 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30005014

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.13e-10	-0.254	1.26
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.22e-10	-1.03	1.87	-0.0276	5.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.46	175.46	179.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.06	4.06	4.06

MAX_MEAN: 0.464 MAX_MED: 0.0285 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid
 CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24
 M4ID: 30004977

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.25e-10	-0.993	4.51
sd:	0.000133	1650	1150000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.53	-2.97	0.445	-2.25	6.53
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.47	172.47	172.68
PROB:	0.91	0.05	0.04
RMSE:	3.62	3.62	3.43

MAX_MEAN: 3.59 MAX_MED: 4.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.09

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol
 CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017
 M4ID: 30004888

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	208.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.55 MAX_MED: -4.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30005028 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.93e-09	0.169	0.956
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.33e-09	0.243	3.66	0.513	4.72
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.39	257.39	261.39
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.02	14.02	14.02

MAX_MEAN: -0.065 MAX_MED: 0.221 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30004791

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.91 MAX_MED: 4.55 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30004858

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.47 MAX_MED: -1.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30004912

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.92 MAX_MED: -3.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30005148

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 16.6 MAX_MED: 16.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30004859

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.3e-05	2.76	7.73
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.18e-09	0.522	7.96	0.789	8.92
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.37	186.37	190.37
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.52	4.52	4.52

MAX_MEAN: 4.34 MAX_MED: 4.21 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30004494

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.2 MAX_MED: -1.82 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30004923

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.16e-12	0.269	1.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.65e-10	0.337	2.26	0.73	4.66
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.33	179.33	183.33
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.92	3.92	3.92

MAX_MEAN: 1.02 MAX_MED: 0.38 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octanoic acid
 CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07
 M4ID: 30004874

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	204.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.19 MAX_MED: -3.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid
 CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23
 M4ID: 30004954

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.04 MAX_MED: -0.123 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Propanol
 CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24
 M4ID: 30004905

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.47e-09 2.75 0.869
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.61e-10 1.68 1.57 1.96 5.06
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.48	184.48	188.48
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.23	4.23	4.23

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.21 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin
 CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07
 M4ID: 30005018

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.29 MAX_MED: -3.29 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate
 CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022
 M4ID: 30004883

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.14e-08 2.7 3.22
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.65 1.69 7.94 1.94 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.37	168.37	171.27
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.55	3.55	3.5

MAX_MEAN: 5.01 MAX_MED: 5.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate
 CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16
 M4ID: 30004625

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.04 2.34 8
 sd: 177 1.81 14.4

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.77e-08 0.0348 6.79 0.297 2.37
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.4	171.81	177.4
PROB:	0.9	0.1	0.01
RMSE:	3.62	3.51	3.62

MAX_MEAN: 2.83 MAX_MED: 2.54 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30004498

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.43 MAX_MED: -1.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: o-Cresol
 CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23
 M4ID: 30004906

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.63	2	8
sd:	1.88	0.24	21.4

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.47e-09	0.0672	6.12	0.343	3.53
sd:	8.38e-05	3080	290000	17300	159000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.14	173.31	178.14
PROB:	0.92	0.07	0.01
RMSE:	3.65	3.62	3.65

MAX_MEAN: 1.24 MAX_MED: 2.55 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlorophen

CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13

M4ID: 30004532

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	210.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.69 MAX_MED: -1.58 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetophenone
 CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08
 M4ID: 30005065

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.386 MAX_MED: -1.92 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30004817

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.12 MAX_MED: 4.71 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30004887

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.1 MAX_MED: -2.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30004911

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.47 MAX_MED: -0.659 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Pentanone
 CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12
 M4ID: 30004485 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.15e-09	1.45	1.02
sd:	0.000144	10200	232000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.43e-09	-0.582	1.65	-0.316	5.34
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.47	224.47	228.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.03	9.03	9.03

MAX_MEAN: -1.76 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone
 CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20
 M4ID: 30004597

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.2 MAX_MED: -1.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate
 CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20
 M4ID: 30005005

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.02e-10 0.877 1.52
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.17e-09 -0.0218 0.907 0.367 6.86
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.25	176.25	180.25
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.61	3.61	3.61

MAX_MEAN: -0.291 MAX_MED: 0.258 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30005079

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.27	1.77	8
sd:	0.839	0.177	15.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.76	-2.58	2.38	-2.14	6.79
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.48	154.19	159.47
PROB:	0.86	0.13	0.01
RMSE:	2.72	2.63	2.69

MAX_MEAN: 2.13 MAX_MED: 2.79 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.14

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30004970

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.4e-10	0.162	1.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.41e-08	0.124	1.23	0.473	4.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.46	182.46	186.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.11	4.11	4.11

MAX_MEAN: -0.55 MAX_MED: 0.347 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: DEET

CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08

M4ID: 30004849

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.19 MAX_MED: 6.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: gamma-Decanolactone
 CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17
 M4ID: 30005152

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	16.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 36.1 MAX_MED: 36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8; 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propanil
 CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24
 M4ID: 30004521

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.81e-08 2.6 2.77
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.97e-07 -0.413 5.06 -0.143 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.96	191.96	195.96
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.97	4.97	4.97

MAX_MEAN: 1.26 MAX_MED: 1.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30004935

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.26 MAX_MED: -3.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bromoxynil

CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21

M4ID: 30004740

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.25e-10	2.01	1.1
sd:	8.8e-05	198	253000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.12e-10	1.53	1.71	1.91	5.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.81	171.81	175.81
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.82	3.82	3.82

MAX_MEAN: 0.641 MAX_MED: 0.737 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenol red

CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06

M4ID: 30004851

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.84 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Digoxin
 CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14
 M4ID: 30005107

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.15e-07 2.75 2.77
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.31e-09 1.4 3.86 1.69 6.44
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.71	225.71	229.71
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.4	8.4	8.4

MAX_MEAN: 4.23 MAX_MED: 4.92 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30005140

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.26e-08	2.76	1.88
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.64e-09	2.14	6.62	2.39	5.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.57	196.57	200.57
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.6	5.6	5.6

MAX_MEAN: 2.15 MAX_MED: 3.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30004629

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.69e-09	2.29	1.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.43e-09	0.761	1.56	1.08	6.12
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.11	187.11	191.11
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.84	5.84	5.84

MAX_MEAN: -0.489 MAX_MED: 1.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate

CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08

M4ID: 30005209

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.99 MAX_MED: 6.85 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetochlor

CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24

M4ID: 30004737

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.73e-09	2.66	2.31
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.07	1.26	2.48	1.51	18
sd:	19.1	1.73	9.47	2.51	242

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.77	170.77	172.47
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	3.7	3.7	3.62

MAX_MEAN: 3.88 MAX_MED: 2.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Anisidine
 CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10
 M4ID: 30005039

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.91e-09 1.37 1.58
 sd: 5.75e-06 2470 63100

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.44e-09 0.173 1.59 0.51 6.49
 sd: 4.92e-05 11300 78800 7840 369000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.8	170.8	174.8
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.39	3.39	3.39

MAX_MEAN: 1.37 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30005111

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.83 MAX_MED: 5.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benfluralin
 CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04
 M4ID: 30004589

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.97 1.75 8
 sd: 0.811 0.14 11.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.19e-06 -2.24 5.12 -1.73 5.41
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.61	148.65	157.61
PROB:	0.62	0.37	0
RMSE:	2.94	2.81	2.94

MAX_MEAN: 3.27 MAX_MED: 3.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.38

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30004933

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.37e-11	-1.7	0.648
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.4e-07	-1.74	2.03	-1.41	4.23
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.31	173.31	177.31
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.47	3.47	3.47

MAX_MEAN: -0.34 MAX_MED: 0.0629 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30004506

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.56 MAX_MED: -3.13 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30004988

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.97 MAX_MED: -3.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene
 CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14
 M4ID: 30004531

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.783 MAX_MED: -1.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol
 CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12
 M4ID: 30004941

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.96e-10 -1.14 0.951
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.67 -3.09 0.683 -1.74 9.42
 sd: 430 161 283 252 3210

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.87	180.87	184.04
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.05	4.05	4.02

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flutolanil
 CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17
 M4ID: 30004696

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.68e-09 2.61 1.19
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.71e-10 2.27 1.36 2.52 6.04
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.68	172.68	176.68
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.64	3.64	3.64

MAX_MEAN: 1.88 MAX_MED: 1.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30004853

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 5.77 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30004878

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.91 MAX_MED: -1.14 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: m-Cresol
 CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19
 M4ID: 30004646

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.35	1.9	8
sd:	1.16	0.12	10.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.25e-10	0.345	0.593	0.769	6.55
sd:	1.13e-05	30400	37500	15500	747000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.6	151.6	161.6
PROB:	0.5	0.5	0
RMSE:	2.74	2.53	2.74

MAX_MEAN: 2.44 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.5

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Molinate

CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13

M4ID: 30005036

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.17 MAX_MED: -2.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen

CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08

M4ID: 30004585

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0384	2.79	7.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.59	1.09	3.08	1.34	11.2
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.23	169.23	169.56
PROB:	0.92	0.05	0.04
RMSE:	3.49	3.49	3.35

MAX_MEAN: 2.82 MAX_MED: 2.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Prometryn
 CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16
 M4ID: 30004697

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.2e-09 2.35 1.06
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.53e-09 1.95 1.22 2.28 4.87
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.06	198.06	202.06
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.38	5.38	5.38

MAX_MEAN: 1.34 MAX_MED: 0.812 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propargite

CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06

M4ID: 30004779

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.69e-05	2.77	7.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.61	0.353	8	0.604	11.8
sd:	116	13.7	306	14.4	888

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.71	195.71	199.69
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.34	5.34	5.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.89 MAX_MED: 5.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate
 CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13
 M4ID: 30004916

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.65 MAX_MED: -2.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Myclobutanil
 CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24
 M4ID: 30005073

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.75e-08 2.65 3.99
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.92 1.31 7.97 1.64 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.4	181.4	182.19
PROB:	0.92	0.05	0.03
RMSE:	4.44	4.44	4.28

MAX_MEAN: 3.64 MAX_MED: 4.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30004601

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.7	1.15	8
sd:	0.722	0.34	17.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.35e-07	-2.44	5.21	-1.8	3.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.04	162.22	171.04
PROB:	0.64	0.36	0
RMSE:	3.44	3.27	3.44

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 3.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.36

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22
 M4ID: 30004619

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.41e-10	2.03	1.4
sd:	2.8e-05	4510	87400

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.95	0.192	5.1	0.636	13.8
sd:	294	24.2	501	17.2	1430

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.92	190.92	194.44
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.96	4.96	4.94

MAX_MEAN: 1.79 MAX_MED: 1.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetic acid
 CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023
 M4ID: 30004882

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.16 MAX_MED: -2.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol
 CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10
 M4ID: 30004919

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.4e-09 1.48 2.09
 sd: 8.78e-05 140 106000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.08e-08 -0.579 7.38 -0.308 3.84
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.49	187.49	191.49
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.4	4.4	4.4

MAX_MEAN: 2.66 MAX_MED: 4.54 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzothiazole

CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02

M4ID: 30005239

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	235.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.04 MAX_MED: 6.47 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30004479

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.78 MAX_MED: -0.649 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Carbendazim
 CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06
 M4ID: 30004491

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0651 MAX_MED: -0.393 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Colchicine

CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06

M4ID: 30004635

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.511	MAX_MED:	-0.815	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cycloheximide

CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09

M4ID: 30005160

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.13e-12	1.36	1.34
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.81e-10	1.72	0.549	2.55	5.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.21	243.21	247.21
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.37	11.37	11.37

MAX_MEAN: 0.264 MAX_MED: 1.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine

CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20

M4ID: 30004573

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.69 MAX_MED: -3.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene
 CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03
 M4ID: 30004566

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.97e-10 0.778 1.27
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2e-09 0.8 1.39 1.16 4.97
 sd: 4.73e-05 33900 47800 21700 457000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.4	171.4	175.4
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.51	3.51	3.51

MAX_MEAN: 0.0936 MAX_MED: 0.378 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30004811

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.45 MAX_MED: 4.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30004985

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0602 MAX_MED: -0.404 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid
 CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12
 M4ID: 30004965

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.221 MAX_MED: -0.646 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30004981

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.65e-11	1.23	0.347
sd:	1.08e-05	34200	184000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.75e-09	0.475	1.79	0.829	5.32
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.81	168.81	172.81
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.25	3.25	3.25

MAX_MEAN: 1.27 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate

CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17

M4ID: 30004936

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.35 MAX_MED: -2.72 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30004910

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.07 MAX_MED: -2.72 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate
 CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20
 M4ID: 30004861

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.44e-11	1.52	1.06
sd:	4.17e-06	3530	95100

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.49e-09	1.42	1.28	2.1	5.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.93	198.93	202.93
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.3	5.3	5.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.667 MAX_MED: 0.542 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30005185

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.28 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30005196 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	248.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	17.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 46.6 MAX_MED: 44.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octhilinone
 CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06
 M4ID: 30004587

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.15e-09	2.78	1.64
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4	1.31	8	1.7	16.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.17	180.17	181.2
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.03
RMSE:	4.86	4.86	4.78

MAX_MEAN: 1.92 MAX_MED: 2.43 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18
 M4ID: 30004671

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.24 MAX_MED: -0.282 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate
CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22
M4ID: 30005051 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.18e-05	2.79	6.21
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.83e-09	1.3	2.14	1.61	7.33
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.14	211.14	215.14
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.53	7.53	7.53

MAX_MEAN: 4.03 MAX_MED: 3.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30005203

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.96 MAX_MED: 5.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Theobromine

CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14

M4ID: 30004867

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.06e-10	-1.26	1.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7e-11	-0.678	0.855	-0.301	5.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.58	180.58	184.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.98	3.98	3.98

MAX_MEAN: 0.755 MAX_MED: 0.253 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30004918

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.19 MAX_MED: -0.912 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triclocarban
 CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21
 M4ID: 30004572

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.68e-11 1.99 1.17
 sd: 9.5e-06 35900 337000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.03e-09 1.83 1.37 2.17 6.19
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.92	183.92	187.92
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.25	4.25	4.25

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate
 CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06
 M4ID: 30004659

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.34e-10 1.82 1
 sd: 1.41e-05 2550 52500

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.52e-10 1.9 1.24 2.22 4.49
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.57	189.57	193.57
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.76	4.76	4.76

MAX_MEAN: 0.446 MAX_MED: 0.633 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30004937

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.21 MAX_MED: -1.35 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30004489

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.83e-10	-0.86	1.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2e-08	-0.497	1.54	-0.196	5.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.52	182.52	186.52
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.28	4.28	4.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.595 MAX_MED: 0.188 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Symclosene
 CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04
 M4ID: 30004661

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.16e-10 1.71 0.849
 sd: 9.94e-06 9490 41400

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.35e-09 0.464 2.68 0.88 5.52
 sd: 6.58e-05 14900 125000 8100 311000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.26	178.26	182.26
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.05	4.05	4.05

MAX_MEAN: 1.14 MAX_MED: 1.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30004862

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.81 MAX_MED: -2.39 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30004490

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.94 MAX_MED: -2.73 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid
 CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14
 M4ID: 30004963

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.996 MAX_MED: -0.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile
 CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18
 M4ID: 30004815

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.88 MAX_MED: 4.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline
 CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18
 M4ID: 30004959

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.72 MAX_MED: -3.58 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine

CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19

M4ID: 30004550

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.96 MAX_MED: -2.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30005056

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.933 MAX_MED: -0.81 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol

CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17

M4ID: 30005128

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 21.2 MAX_MED: 21.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30004940

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.56 MAX_MED: -1.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol

CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16

M4ID: 30004577

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.35e-10	1.91	1.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.65e-10	1.76	1.07	2.47	5.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.9	209.9	213.9
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.04	7.04	7.04

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30004871

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.16e-10	-0.985	2.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.96e-09	-0.612	3.84	-0.325	4.42
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.46	204.46	208.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.01	6.01	6.01

MAX_MEAN: 1.81 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30004890

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.648 MAX_MED: -0.804 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene

CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20

M4ID: 30004621

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.952 MAX_MED: -2.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide
 CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08
 M4ID: 30004873

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.95 MAX_MED: -3.55 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30004670

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.924 MAX_MED: -0.837 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride
 CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06
 M4ID: 30004683

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.38e-09 2.55 0.964
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.67e-08 -0.31 3.79 -0.00644 6.4
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	232.4	238.4	242.4
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.38	10.38	10.38

MAX_MEAN: 1.59 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate
 CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05
 M4ID: 30004924

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.472 MAX_MED: -1.29 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30005055

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.965 MAX_MED: -1.74 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30004694

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.33 MAX_MED: -1.09 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate
 CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020
 M4ID: 30004501

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.424 MAX_MED: -1.45 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Malic acid
 CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12
 M4ID: 30004869

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.65e-09 0.082 1.07
 sd: 0.000321 16500 65800

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.43e-09 -0.295 7.97 0.471 2.47
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.95	220.95	224.95
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.08	8.08	8.08

MAX_MEAN: 0.811 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30004553

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.142 MAX_MED: -0.385 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol
 CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23
 M4ID: 30004594

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	114.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.33 MAX_MED: -1.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30005189

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.84 MAX_MED: 6.69 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate

CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24

M4ID: 30004809

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.19 MAX_MED: 5.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate

CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23

M4ID: 30004930

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	238.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.992 MAX_MED: -0.655 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30005045

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.39 MAX_MED: 4.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30005010

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.44e-10	0.164	1.19
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.05e-08	0.161	1.72	0.668	4.84
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.57	187.57	191.57
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.53	4.53	4.53

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 0.0213 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methylionone

CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17

M4ID: 30004864

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.35 MAX_MED: -0.325 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30004637

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.57e-06	2.77	5.52
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.2	0.757	3.83	1.44	17.9
sd:	4.55	0.659	11.2	2.25	196

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	216.15	222.15	222.52
PROB:	0.92	0.05	0.04
RMSE:	8.38	8.38	8.08

MAX_MEAN: 5.19 MAX_MED: 5.69 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfate

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30005004

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.09e-08	2.7	0.628
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.26	1.16	7.99	1.93	18
sd:	1.45	0.345	17.9	0.0576	21.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.67	200.67	198.79
PROB:	0.85	0.04	0.11
RMSE:	6.82	6.82	6.63

MAX_MEAN: 3.43 MAX_MED: 3.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.15

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30004613

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.623 MAX_MED: -1.15 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene

CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17

M4ID: 30005200 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	311.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	38.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 63.3 MAX_MED: 65.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Limonene
 CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23
 M4ID: 30005026

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.49 MAX_MED: -1.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Silica
 CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17
 M4ID: 30005008

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.9 2.01 8
 sd: 1.8 0.142 12.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.59e-10 0.406 2.48 0.84 5.29
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.05	173.09	180.05
PROB:	0.82	0.18	0.01
RMSE:	3.83	3.68	3.83

MAX_MEAN: 2.94 MAX_MED: 1.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.18

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate
 CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20
 M4ID: 30004525

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.91e-10	-2.07	1.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.7e-09	-1.47	1.4	-0.965	4.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.95	164.95	168.95
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.08	3.08	3.08

MAX_MEAN: 0.35 MAX_MED: 0.0223 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate

CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10

M4ID: 30004631 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.78e-09	2.69	1.73
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.4e-08	1.33	1.56	1.59	6.26
sd:	0.000154	8220	38400	3950	139000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	225.28	231.28	235.28
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.02	10.02	10.02

MAX_MEAN: 0.621 MAX_MED: 1.87 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl
 CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04
 M4ID: 30004829

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.54 MAX_MED: 6.47 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride
 CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16
 M4ID: 30004649

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.67e-10 0.6 1.37
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.64e-10 -0.0187 2.38 0.405 5.28
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.63	169.63	173.63
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.35	3.35	3.35

MAX_MEAN: 1.86 MAX_MED: 1.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triclosan
 CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006
 M4ID: 30004515

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.74e-10	2.44	1.21
sd:	1.43e-05	29100	113000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.15	1.33	7.95	1.67	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.86	190.86	194.05
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.3	5.3	5.27

MAX_MEAN: 1.53 MAX_MED: 1.93 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bifenazate
 CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22
 M4ID: 30004691

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.94e-08 2.67 4.17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.61e-11 2.13 0.825 4.17 5.92
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.12	194.12	198.12
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.12	5.12	5.12

MAX_MEAN: 4.88 MAX_MED: 4.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)
 CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11
 M4ID: 30004750

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	236.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.2 MAX_MED: -0.107 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluazinam
 CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01
 M4ID: 30004856

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.00019 2.79 7.55
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4e-09 1.49 1.88 1.79 5.65
 sd: 1.08e-05 22000 49200 12300 169000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.66	198.66	202.66
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.32	5.32	5.32

MAX_MEAN: 2.45 MAX_MED: 2.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flufenacet

CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16

M4ID: 30004913

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.59 MAX_MED: -1.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Prallethrin
 CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019
 M4ID: 30004886

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.53e-10	1.41	1.29
sd:	3.18e-05	7130	156000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.77e-09	1.93	1.78	2.21	4.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.97	197.97	201.97
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.8	5.8	5.8

MAX_MEAN: 0.5 MAX_MED: 0.299 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyridaben

CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09

M4ID: 30004560

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.4 MAX_MED: -1.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin

CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24

M4ID: 30004617

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.52e-09	2.02	1.32
sd:	3.1e-05	3470	44900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.91e-11	2.03	1.52	2.77	3.64
sd:	2.02e-06	8640	123000	14100	1160000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.6	199.6	203.6
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.7	5.7	5.7

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30004889

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.926 MAX_MED: -1.04 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin
 CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24
 M4ID: 30004569

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.00138 2.78 7.86
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.03e-10 1.84 1.76 2.17 5.54
 sd: 3.05e-05 31800 126000 46100 273000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.99	220.99	224.99
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.69	7.69	7.69

MAX_MEAN: 1.49 MAX_MED: 1.72 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide

CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04

M4ID: 30005165

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.9 MAX_MED: 4.84 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos
 CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21
 M4ID: 30004524

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.633 MAX_MED: -0.421 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Haloperidol

CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14

M4ID: 30005227

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.33 MAX_MED: 6.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad
 CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06
 M4ID: 30004707

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.37e-10 2.57 0.912
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.69e-09 1.41 1.78 1.75 5.29
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	225.3	231.3	235.3
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.12	9.12	9.12

MAX_MEAN: 2 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Metconazole

CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011

M4ID: 30004894 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.98e-08	2.42	4.66
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.3	1.3	8	1.71	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.03	226.03	224.25
PROB:	0.85	0.04	0.1
RMSE:	9.58	9.58	9.19

MAX_MEAN: 6.69 MAX_MED: 7.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.15

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl
 CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21
 M4ID: 30005124

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.69 MAX_MED: 9.18 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30004978

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.55 MAX_MED: -1.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethofumesate
 CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17
 M4ID: 30004600

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.16e-10 2.79 1.45
 sd: 1.28e-06 98300 343000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.04 1.61 3.34 1.9 18
 sd: 47.9 3.45 13.6 0.278 19.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.42	169.42	166.5
PROB:	0.79	0.04	0.17
RMSE:	3.42	3.42	3.17

MAX_MEAN: 3.27 MAX_MED: 3.69 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.21

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30005042

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.7 MAX_MED: -0.724 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin
 CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05
 M4ID: 30005020

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.39 MAX_MED: -2.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexaconazole

CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003

M4ID: 30004902

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00155	2.79	7.89
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.18e-09	2.3	3.04	4.29	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.71	204.71	208.71
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.77	6.77	6.77

MAX_MEAN: 7.48 MAX_MED: 7.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium warfarin
 CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17
 M4ID: 30004960

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.91e-09 1.91 1.02
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.72e-09 0.0354 3.04 0.39 4.07
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.59	173.59	177.59
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.55	3.55	3.55

MAX_MEAN: 1.88 MAX_MED: 1.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30004492

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.13 MAX_MED: 2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride
 CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17
 M4ID: 30004624

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.2e-10 2.55 1.79
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.17e-08 0.85 1.63 1.14 7.51
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.29	160.29	164.29
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.12	3.12	3.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.77 MAX_MED: 1.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride
 CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10
 M4ID: 30004775 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.38e-09 2.45 1.46
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.57 -0.0249 6.21 0.977 16.8
 sd: 3.76 5.87 1470 1.09 790

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	223.31	229.31	232.64
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.03	10.03	9.98

MAX_MEAN: 2.56 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate

CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23

M4ID: 30004666

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.22 MAX_MED: -1.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30005012

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.54 MAX_MED: -1.38 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride
 CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017
 M4ID: 30004504

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.66 MAX_MED: -1.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30004529

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.22	MAX_MED:	-1.38	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenuron
 CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08
 M4ID: 30004993

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	$3.7\text{e-}10$	-1.8	1.52
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	$9.52\text{e-}08$	-1.61	1.18	-1.35	6.22
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.43	190.43	194.43
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.76	4.76	4.76

MAX_MEAN: -0.979 MAX_MED: 0.503 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate
 CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06
 M4ID: 30004755

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.12e-09 2.77 1.48
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.27 1.29 2.72 1.75 18
 sd: 13 0.719 3.6 0.305 34.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.5	187.5	182.88
PROB:	0.65	0.03	0.32
RMSE:	5.12	5.12	4.76

MAX_MEAN: 4.91 MAX_MED: 6.16 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.35

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid

CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09

M4ID: 30004968

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	239.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.87 MAX_MED: -3.45 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide
 CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21
 M4ID: 30004644

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.3e-10	2.09	1.26
sd:	9.79e-06	5500	37200

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.56e-09	1.79	2.39	2.27	4.84
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.62	191.62	195.62
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.87	4.87	4.87

MAX_MEAN: 0.539 MAX_MED: 0.759 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid
 CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15
 M4ID: 30004554

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.82e-10 -0.732 1.17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.87e-09 -0.684 1.29 -0.27 5.1
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.25	175.25	179.25
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.64	3.64	3.64

MAX_MEAN: -0.0364 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7

CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011

M4ID: 30004510

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.25 MAX_MED: -1.48 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30005145

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.46 MAX_MED: 7.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30004606 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	226.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.36 MAX_MED: -2.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate
 CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16
 M4ID: 30005033

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.56e-11 0.432 0.792
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.98e-12 0.364 1.56 0.722 5.7
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.22	169.22	173.22
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.27	3.27	3.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.296 MAX_MED: 0.481 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium
 CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23
 M4ID: 30004474

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.2 MAX_MED: -1.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butylene carbonate
 CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19
 M4ID: 30004574

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.18 MAX_MED: -0.862 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dinocap
 CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22
 M4ID: 30004739

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.011 2.79 7.88
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.38e-08 2.29 6.78 2.56 0.376
 sd: 0.00108 1170 117000 9320 12900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.88	220.88	224.88
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.69	7.69	7.69

MAX_MEAN: 4.11 MAX_MED: 3.28 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Niclosamide
 CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24
 M4ID: 30004833

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.3 2.79 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.82e-10 2.3 7.59 3.31 17.5
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.9	225.9	229.9
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.32	8.32	8.32

MAX_MEAN: 8.64 MAX_MED: 8.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diniconazole
 CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06
 M4ID: 30004803

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.52e-08	2.67	2.49
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.57e-08	1.99	0.372	4.22	10.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.18	215.18	219.18
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.37	7.37	7.37

MAX_MEAN: 6.99 MAX_MED: 7.57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30004618

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.12 MAX_MED: -1.82 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octyl gallate

CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19

M4ID: 30004598

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.23e-09	1.33	1.09
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.12e-09	1.69	1.29	2.1	4.78
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.99	198.99	202.99
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.81	5.81	5.81

MAX_MEAN: 0.389 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30005117

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.58e-08	2.78	3.39
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.72e-09	1.14	7.98	1.55	13.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.64	189.64	193.64
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5	5	5

MAX_MEAN: 4.35 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin
 CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23
 M4ID: 30004570

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.11 MAX_MED: -0.689 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30005040

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.41 MAX_MED: -1.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanolsulfate, sodium salt

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30004526

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.79 MAX_MED: -1.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30004961

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.69 MAX_MED: -0.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30005237

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 9.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bromophenol blue

CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02

M4ID: 30005191

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.16e-10	2.77	2.63
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.83	0.27	7.98	0.52	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.01	247.01	251
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.83	4.83	4.83

MAX_MEAN: 4.24 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30004987

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.691 MAX_MED: -0.665 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite
 CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15
 M4ID: 30004914

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.81e-10	0.167	1.49
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.21e-10	0.456	2.24	0.849	4.9
sd:	5.73e-05	53300	280000	43500	545000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.45	182.45	186.45
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.08	4.08	4.08

MAX_MEAN: 1.48 MAX_MED: 0.841 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate

CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05

M4ID: 30004876

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.69	MAX_MED:	-1.38	BMAD:	1.48
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COFF:	14.8	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flufenoxuron
 CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01
 M4ID: 30005144

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.43e-09 2.69 1.83
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.82e-09 1.91 1.37 2.2 4.99
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	208.05	214.05	218.05
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.04	3.04	3.04

MAX_MEAN: 2.34 MAX_MED: 1.86 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid
 CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20
 M4ID: 30004813

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.02e-09	2.71	2.57
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.722	0.529	7.97	1.4	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.26	161.26	164.82
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	2.97	2.97	2.95

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 3.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate
 CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07
 M4ID: 30004946

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.93 MAX_MED: -1.82 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline
 CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08
 M4ID: 30004921

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.06e-10	-1.07	1.63
sd:	1.21e-05	12100	153000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.07e-06	-1.73	2.23	-1.44	6.43
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.68	189.68	193.68
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.62	4.62	4.62

MAX_MEAN: -0.234 MAX_MED: 1.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea
 CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016
 M4ID: 30004505

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.14e-11	0.208	0.963
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.96e-08	-0.541	4.6	-0.265	2.92
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.59	181.59	185.59
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.02	4.02	4.02

MAX_MEAN: 0.00573 MAX_MED: 0.89 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone
 CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11
 M4ID: 30004942 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.99e-08 2.78 3.18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.65 0.823 4.24 1.69 17.7
 sd: 2.92 0.818 15 0.116 156

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.86	202.86	205.05
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	6.66	6.66	6.57

MAX_MEAN: 2.66 MAX_MED: 3.44 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine
 CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11
 M4ID: 30004654

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	225.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.74 MAX_MED: -1.95 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide

CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11

M4ID: 30005134

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.21e-10	2.62	0.347
sd:	7.07e-06	30000	10300

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.91e-09	1.79	1.53	2.08	5.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.7	183.7	187.7
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.5	4.5	4.5

MAX_MEAN: 0.79 MAX_MED: 0.466 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30005183

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.08 MAX_MED: 8.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate

CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04

M4ID: 30004877 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.56e-10	2.34	0.335
sd:	9.6e-06	129000	54500

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.03e-10	2.02	1.19	2.35	5.76
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.27	221.27	225.27
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.16	8.16	8.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.652 MAX_MED: 1.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid

CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19

M4ID: 30004478

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.76 MAX_MED: -4.93 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30004872

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.7 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyltrioctylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30005232 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.227	2.79	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.58	-3.53	6.61	0.0199	9.71
sd:	4.56	160	1280	1.64	791

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.89	255.89	258.21
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.04	14.04	13.77

MAX_MEAN: 7.96 MAX_MED: 7.48 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30004578

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.84e-08	2.62	1.02
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.93e-10	0.0185	5.53	0.381	6.07
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.15	175.15	179.15
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.71	3.71	3.71

MAX_MEAN: 2.5 MAX_MED: 2.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30004964

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.56 MAX_MED: -1.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol
 CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04
 M4ID: 30004541

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.59e-10 2.79 1.94
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.36 1.77 8 2.02 12.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.45	166.45	169.77
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.28	3.28	3.26

MAX_MEAN: 1.66 MAX_MED: 2.45 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate
 CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15
 M4ID: 30004866

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.14 MAX_MED: 0.0213 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30004881

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.38e-10	-0.632	1.46
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.44e-09	-0.534	1.8	-0.0941	5.46
sd:	3.27e-05	55000	135000	7210	574000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.14	191.14	195.14
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.83	4.83	4.83

MAX_MEAN: 1.6 MAX_MED: 0.974 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CI-959

CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09

M4ID: 30004632

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.18 MAX_MED: -1.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30004994

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.46 MAX_MED: -3.55 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CI-1044
 CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08
 M4ID: 30005089

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.12e-12 -0.435 1.34
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.27e-10 -0.764 1.54 0.54 5.34
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.85	180.85	184.85
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4	4	4

MAX_MEAN: 1.85 MAX_MED: 1.06 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: CP-863187

CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14

M4ID: 30005011

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	$3.58\text{e-}10$	0.252	1.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	$1.88\text{e-}09$	0.332	1.08	0.588	5.14
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.04	200.04	204.04
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.44	5.44	5.44

MAX_MEAN: 0.156 MAX_MED: 0.135 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30004839

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.56 MAX_MED: 5.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SSR180711
 CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24
 M4ID: 30004857

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.86e-10 -0.331 2.23
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.89 -3.31 1.94 -2.29 6.16
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.71	186.71	189.36
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.57	4.57	4.49

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 2.79 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SSR 103800
 CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01
 M4ID: 30004880

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.69 MAX_MED: -1.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30004528

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.39 MAX_MED: -2.17 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Potassium chlorate

CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16

M4ID: 30004673

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.472 MAX_MED: -0.648 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30004969

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.2e-10	-1.07	2.03
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.000873	-1.83	4.73	-1.57	8.21
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.42	162.42	166.42
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.44	4.44	4.44

MAX_MEAN: 0.602 MAX_MED: 1.68 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline

CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04

M4ID: 30004973 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.38e-08	2.69	2.73
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.46e-09	2.21	1.96	2.62	4.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.17	240.17	244.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.01	11.01	11.01

MAX_MEAN: 1.75 MAX_MED: 2.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octylparaben
 CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02
 M4ID: 30005215

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.51 MAX_MED: 5.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: FR167356

CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05

M4ID: 30004708

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.38 MAX_MED: -0.973 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Lauryl gallate
 CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01
 M4ID: 30005072

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.36e-09	2.73	0.964
sd:	1.78e-05	11200	24000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.66	1	8	1.71	18
sd:	1.15	0.151	40.6	0.0802	66.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.31	193.31	193.28
PROB:	0.91	0.05	0.05
RMSE:	2.48	2.48	2.37

MAX_MEAN: 1.95 MAX_MED: 1.52 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.09

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505
 CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007
 M4ID: 30004898

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.32 MAX_MED: -4.83 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)
 CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08
 M4ID: 30004945

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.66e-09 -0.114 2.57
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.06e-07 -2.18 3.05 -1.27 9.28
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.29	182.29	186.29
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.15	4.15	4.15

MAX_MEAN: 3.8 MAX_MED: 4.18 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ziram
 CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08
 M4ID: 30005233 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.00128 2.79 7.28
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.5 -0.436 0.3 0.164 2.15
 sd: 41.6 7.91 0.402 1.76 3.17

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.97	257.97	260.19
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	14.66	14.66	14.37

MAX_MEAN: 9.3 MAX_MED: 8.82 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene
 CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10
 M4ID: 30004943

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 12 2.34 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.73e-10 1.24 1.16 1.54 7.08
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.89	194.37	199.89
PROB:	0.9	0.1	0.01
RMSE:	5.18	5.01	5.18

MAX_MEAN: 4.12 MAX_MED: 3.69 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nilutamide
 CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06
 M4ID: 30004971

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 40.9 2.8 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 31.5 -0.329 7.85 -0.0786 12.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	250.11	256.11	259.93
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	19.57	19.57	19.41

MAX_MEAN: 39.8 MAX_MED: 57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30005156

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.32	1.78	4.69
sd:	0.623	0.0654	2.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.97	1.87	3.15	2.32	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.61	116.07	118.65
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	2.62	1.45	1.43

MAX_MEAN: 4.57 MAX_MED: 4.66 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30004502

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.2	1.94	8
sd:	2.16	0.0473	7.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.2	1.94	8	4.27	4.13
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.19	183.06	187.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.23	4.18	4.18

MAX_MEAN: 11.1 MAX_MED: 11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol
 CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002
 M4ID: 30004903

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.43 1.87 5.99
 sd: 1.2 0.0745 4.95

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.88 1.91 4.94 2.43 4.4
 sd: 25.5 0.471 5.8 4.93 226

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	220.06	198.71	202.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.55	2.5	2.5

MAX_MEAN: 5.4 MAX_MED: 5.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene
 CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06
 M4ID: 30004563

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.95 1.91 5.68
 sd: 1.8 0.0689 5.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.96 1.91 5.67 2.61 7.64
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.46	158.09	162.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.85	2.92	2.92

MAX_MEAN: 8.93 MAX_MED: 6.74 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30004751

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.23	1.15	1.18
sd:	2.27	0.49	1.49

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.23	1.15	1.18	3.66	6.05
sd:	2.27	0.49	1.48	1770	7950

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.83	148.86	152.86
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.5	2.68	2.68

MAX_MEAN: 7.64 MAX_MED: 5.91 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol
 CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18
 M4ID: 30005103

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 10.9 1.3 2.03
 sd: 3.12 0.267 1.96

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.9 1.3 2.03 3.59 6.12
 sd: 3.12 0.267 1.96 766 3650

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.7	151.95	155.95
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.13	2.5	2.5

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 14.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30005067

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.16	1.88	4.56
sd:	2.91	0.183	5.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.16	1.88	4.56	3.82	4.49
sd:	2.91	0.183	5.23	1060	3210

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.96	158.74	162.74
PROB:	0.06	0.83	0.11
RMSE:	3.57	2.88	2.88

MAX_MEAN: 5.03 MAX_MED: 5.53 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.94

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Eugeno1

CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17

M4ID: 30004984

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.63	1.56	2.98
sd:	1.47	0.184	1.47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.82	1.64	2.61	2.39	7.19
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.84	172.95	176.65
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	6.04	3.54	3.53

MAX_MEAN: 8.79 MAX_MED: 8.31 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Methyl carbamate
 CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22
 M4ID: 30004835

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.59 -3.7 6.2
 sd: 0.827 367 2280

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.59 -3.7 5.97 4.3 3.24
 sd: 0.827 288 1720 1200 1860

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	197.27	184.25	188.25
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.36	4.57	4.57

MAX_MEAN: 7.29 MAX_MED: 7.18 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nicotine
 CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07
 M4ID: 30005162

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.78 1.12 2.93
 sd: 0.636 0.153 2.34

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.92 1.13 2.73 2.36 17.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	167.08	136.97	140.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.59	2	2

MAX_MEAN: 5.74 MAX_MED: 6.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30004626

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.23 1.92 5.57
 sd: 1.96 0.0613 4.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.23 1.92 5.57 4.22 15.3
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	178.28	160.3	164.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.36	2.92	2.92

MAX_MEAN: 7.48 MAX_MED: 8.78 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20
 M4ID: 30005221

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5 1.16 0.792
 sd: 1.74 0.499 0.596

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.34 1.87 0.618 2.62 1.15
 sd: 23.7 2.91 0.593 1.21 2.65

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.76	129.51	133.26
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	3.5	1.9	1.89

MAX_MEAN: 5.65 MAX_MED: 5.97 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Retinol acetate
 CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05
 M4ID: 30005092

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.73 1.07 8
 sd: 0.456 0.128 12.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.99 1.88 1.11 2.28 16.1
 sd: 6.45 0.712 0.458 0.0317 20

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.02	131.74	132.94
PROB:	0	0.64	0.36
RMSE:	2.72	1.93	1.84

MAX_MEAN: 4.97 MAX_MED: 4.84 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Decanal
 CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24
 M4ID: 30005121

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.89 -0.505 8
 sd: 0.476 3.19 51.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.2 1.21 0.3 1.74 2.46
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.58	147.7	149.28
PROB:	0.02	0.67	0.3
RMSE:	2.92	2.39	2.3

MAX_MEAN: 3.98 MAX_MED: 4.89 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthol
 CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01
 M4ID: 30004736

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.15 1.94 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 11.2 1.96 8 2.32 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.26	112.5	113.4
PROB:	0	0.61	0.39
RMSE:	3.65	1.38	1.39

MAX_MEAN: 7.98 MAX_MED: 8.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propoxur
 CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08
 M4ID: 30004729

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.2 1.13 5.59
 sd: 0.459 0.119 4.43

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.63 1.16 4.54 2.32 17.5
 sd: 0.534 0.0978 3.13 0.0206 20.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.6	124.94	126.49
PROB:	0	0.68	0.32
RMSE:	3.41	1.66	1.61

MAX_MEAN: 5.23 MAX_MED: 5.41 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate
 CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19
 M4ID: 30004958

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.74 1.96 3.38
 sd: 2.21 0.122 3.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.41 2.01 3.22 2.43 6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	170.42	154.82	158.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.83	2.73	2.73

MAX_MEAN: 7.2 MAX_MED: 7.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30004929

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.05	0.837	8
sd:	0.759	0.392	15.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.26	0.862	8	2.4	2.16
sd:	1.17	0.415	17.3	0.972	8.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.73	162.29	166.15
PROB:	0.3	0.61	0.09
RMSE:	3.55	3.12	3.11

MAX_MEAN: 3.74 MAX_MED: 4.71 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.7

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Melatonin
 CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07
 M4ID: 30005138

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.24 1.79 1.5
 sd: 2.82 0.674 2.38

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.29 1.97 8 2.29 12.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.6	150.55	153.52
PROB:	0.33	0.55	0.12
RMSE:	2.77	2.45	2.44

MAX_MEAN: 3.34 MAX_MED: 5.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.67

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene
 CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06
 M4ID: 30005163

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.71 1.59 0.3
 sd: 5.51 2.16 0.24

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.71 1.59 0.3 2.72 16.8
 sd: 5.51 2.16 0.24 70.5 2710

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.13	124.33	128.33
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.74	1.68	1.68

MAX_MEAN: 5.39 MAX_MED: 5.19 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butylate
 CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05
 M4ID: 30004828

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.93 2.27 0.782
 sd: 7.53 1.04 0.457

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.93 2.27 0.782 3.17 9.16
 sd: 7.53 1.04 0.457 1560 16400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.15	115.3	119.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.6	1.44	1.44

MAX_MEAN: 4.81 MAX_MED: 6.25 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dicamba
 CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10
 M4ID: 30004847

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.73 1.55 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.79 1.57 0.3 3.62 5.89
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	151.08	129.11	133.11
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.84	1.73	1.73

MAX_MEAN: 3.43 MAX_MED: 4.62 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fomesafen
 CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16
 M4ID: 30004841

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.89 -3.7 6.65
 sd: 0.364 333 2220

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.75 -3.69 6.71 0.954 13.5
 sd: 0.67 366 2490 1.77 516

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	151.07	137.93	147.12
PROB:	0	0.99	0.01
RMSE:	2.79	2.08	2.15

MAX_MEAN: 3.93 MAX_MED: 4.63 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyrene

CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23

M4ID: 30004546

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.66	1.39	8
sd:	0.878	0.156	11.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.2	1.4	7.96	1.97	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.58	153.37	157.14
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	4.74	2.78	2.79

MAX_MEAN: 6.52 MAX_MED: 5.52 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Terbaci1

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30004996

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.21	1.97	8
sd:	1.05	0.0677	8.51

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.07e-09	0.154	6.18	0.463	5.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.69	152.22	164.69
PROB:	0.23	0.77	0
RMSE:	3	2.74	3

MAX_MEAN: 3.03 MAX_MED: 2.97 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.77

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butanal oxime
 CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12
 M4ID: 30005229

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.09 1.08 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.7 2.07 0.3 2.32 18
 sd: 23.6 5.97 0.572 0.053 49.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.43	166.36	169.93
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	4.76	3.26	3.24

MAX_MEAN: 5.64 MAX_MED: 6.65 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone
 CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12
 M4ID: 30005157

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.85	1.23	8
sd:	0.671	0.0862	7.62

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.85	1.23	8	2.61	7.76
sd:	0.936	0.0888	7.63	24.6	429

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.77	146.94	150.94
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.8	2.43	2.43

MAX_MEAN: 7.34 MAX_MED: 6.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate
 CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24
 M4ID: 30005217

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.31 -3.68 6.83
 sd: 0.82 343 2390

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.31 -3.7 6.26 3.95 3.98
 sd: 0.82 215 1350 723 1700

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	212.97	182.46	186.46
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.65	4.21	4.21

MAX_MEAN: 8.84 MAX_MED: 8.69 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene
 CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22
 M4ID: 30004667

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.54	1.96	8
sd:	0.761	0.0361	5.63

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.54	1.96	8	4.12	5.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.36	112.12	116.12
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.12	1.32	1.32

MAX_MEAN: 4.23 MAX_MED: 4.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate
 CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06
 M4ID: 30005211

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.49 2.6 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.49 2.3 0.3 3.14 18
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.94	141.12	145.11
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.4	2.35	2.35

MAX_MEAN: 4.98 MAX_MED: 4.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate
 CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13
 M4ID: 30005228

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.85	-1.68	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.33	-1.01	0.3	2.31	17.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167	120.41	122.7
PROB:	0	0.76	0.24
RMSE:	3.54	1.6	1.55

MAX_MEAN: 6.12 MAX_MED: 7.18 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol
 CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08
 M4ID: 30004681

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.7 2.06 1.85
 sd: 10 0.814 2.09

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.7 2.06 1.85 3.54 5.65
 sd: 10 0.814 2.09 2020 9300

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	125.99	124.54	128.54
PROB:	0.3	0.62	0.08
RMSE:	3.52	3	3

MAX_MEAN: 5.08 MAX_MED: 5.08 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.7

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: DINP branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30005070

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.18	0.992	3.03
sd:	0.755	0.288	4.47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.18	0.992	3.03	3.8	4.46
sd:	0.755	0.288	4.47	720	2090

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.71	115.39	119.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.19	2.74	2.74

MAX_MEAN: 5.75 MAX_MED: 5.75 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenofibrate
 CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05
 M4ID: 30005068

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.79 1.62 2.54
 sd: 1.29 0.395 2.74

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.8 2.02 6.18 2.27 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	152.51	145.89	147.99
PROB:	0.03	0.72	0.25
RMSE:	3.11	2.57	2.45

MAX_MEAN: 5.33 MAX_MED: 4.82 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30005139

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.46	0.59	1.85
sd:	0.526	0.22	1.07

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.6	1.14	1.27	1.79	0.839
sd:	21.6	0.661	0.702	1.73	0.92

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.92	138.14	138.66
PROB:	0	0.56	0.44
RMSE:	4.18	2.12	1.98

MAX_MEAN: 7.36 MAX_MED: 7.22 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide
 CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16
 M4ID: 30004721

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.95 2.26 2.91
 sd: 22.7 0.824 4.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.95 2.26 2.91 4.27 14.9
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	152.29	147.53	151.53
PROB:	0.08	0.81	0.11
RMSE:	2.85	2.28	2.28

MAX_MEAN: 5.1 MAX_MED: 5.26 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.92

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Etridiazole
 CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08
 M4ID: 30004753

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 10.2 1.42 0.968
 sd: 3.22 0.399 0.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.2 1.42 0.968 3.46 6.91
 sd: 3.22 0.399 0.41 932 5560

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.98	133.59	137.59
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.5	2.02	2.02

MAX_MEAN: 9.31 MAX_MED: 9.91 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tefluthrin

CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013

M4ID: 30004892

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.35	1.41	8
sd:	0.766	0.245	14.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.55	1.42	8	2.34	15.9
sd:	0.873	0.305	18.3	0.168	63.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.01	154.81	158.55
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	4.21	2.63	2.61

MAX_MEAN: 6.08 MAX_MED: 6.55 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyproconazole
CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03
M4ID: 30005022

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.37	1.24	4.81
sd:	0.597	0.0589	2.76

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.02	1.25	4.34	2.32	17.9
sd:	0.727	0.0507	2.45	0.0159	13.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.69	140.79	141.13
PROB:	0	0.54	0.46
RMSE:	5.74	2.32	2.17

MAX_MEAN: 11.1 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenitrothion

CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018

M4ID: 30004503

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.47	1.88	1.9
sd:	2.55	0.199	1.43

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.2	2.04	1.96	2.33	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.36	139.14	142.73
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	3.71	2.1	2.07

MAX_MEAN: 6.29 MAX_MED: 6.63 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide
 CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16
 M4ID: 30005129

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.39 2.12 1.19
 sd: 3.61 0.355 0.745

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.39 2.12 1.19 3.87 5.07
 sd: 3.61 0.355 0.745 1050 3410

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.13	133.84	137.84
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.85	2.04	2.04

MAX_MEAN: 5.41 MAX_MED: 5.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tepra loxydim

CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09

M4ID: 30004800

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.44	1.53	1.74
sd:	1.51	0.427	1.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.79	2.04	1.66	2.29	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.17	143.35	146.04
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	4.32	3.43	3.51

MAX_MEAN: 7.98 MAX_MED: 4.84 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30004939

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.45	1.89	8
sd:	1.39	0.0556	6.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.45	1.89	8	3.91	5.01
sd:	1.39	0.0556	6.28	2160	6760

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.27	146.09	150.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.01	2.23	2.23

MAX_MEAN: 7.73 MAX_MED: 8.42 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Azamethiphos
 CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03
 M4ID: 30004614

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 10.9 2.21 3.29
 sd: 12 0.359 2.98

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.9 2.21 3.29 4.09 3.98
 sd: 12 0.359 2.98 2020 4530

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	166.11	160.64	164.64
PROB:	0.05	0.83	0.11
RMSE:	3.68	2.92	2.92

MAX_MEAN: 6.79 MAX_MED: 8.64 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.95

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thymo1
 CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13
 M4ID: 30005132

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.76 1.4 2.29
 sd: 0.986 0.132 0.903

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.73 1.49 1.88 2.34 17.9
 sd: 2.69 0.261 0.91 0.0403 22.2

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	184.45	130.01	133.63
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	4.89	1.81	1.78

MAX_MEAN: 9.03 MAX_MED: 9.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30004980

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.56	1.84	8
sd:	0.824	0.0649	5.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.56	1.84	8	4.28	5.93
sd:	0.824	0.0649	5.9	164000	474000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.62	130.27	134.27
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.88	1.74	1.74

MAX_MEAN: 4.59 MAX_MED: 5.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butyl benzoate
 CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15
 M4ID: 30004818

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.95	1.65	2.04
sd:	1.02	0.128	1.09

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.07	1.88	1.58	2.36	8.18
sd:	12	0.737	1.21	0.0915	19.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.48	126.57	130.2
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	3.61	1.72	1.69

MAX_MEAN: 6.13 MAX_MED: 5.54 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride
 CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009
 M4ID: 30004896

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 11.6 1.76 5.79
 sd: 2.17 0.0739 4.34

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 11.6 1.76 5.79 4.28 5.52
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	206.49	174	178
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.17	3.59	3.59

MAX_MEAN: 11.8 MAX_MED: 11.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine
 CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10
 M4ID: 30005207

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.31 1.2 1.18
 sd: 2.15 0.533 1.18

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 11.8 2.08 0.702 2.33 7.82
 sd: 25.9 2.47 0.63 0.137 31.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.87	161	164.21
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	4.71	3.3	3.3

MAX_MEAN: 7.02 MAX_MED: 6.88 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate

CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20

M4ID: 30005197

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.06	1.86	0.77
sd:	4.57	0.803	0.457

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.06	1.86	0.77	3.54	6.43
sd:	4.57	0.803	0.457	1630	8490

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.65	119.32	123.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.18	1.73	1.73

MAX_MEAN: 4.96 MAX_MED: 5.03 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Clove leaf oil
 CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09
 M4ID: 30005184

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.31 1.03 2.6
 sd: 0.77 0.0899 1.22

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.75 1.06 2.36 2.58 2.76
 sd: 1.79 0.131 1.24 0.862 9.54

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.52	142.25	145.79
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	7.13	2.27	2.22

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 9.91 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30004548

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.93	1.67	8
sd:	0.456	0.0561	9.22

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.81	1.68	7.99	4.3	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.25	118.83	122.77
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.69	1.49	1.49

MAX_MEAN: 4.09 MAX_MED: 4.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate

CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02

M4ID: 30004855

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.41	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.17	-3.05	3.16	4.26	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.29	124.9	128.62
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	4.6	1.69	1.64

MAX_MEAN: 5.99 MAX_MED: 6.36 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonic acid

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30004796

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.38	1.48	1.86
sd:	0.722	0.225	1.11

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.81	2.04	1.39	2.3	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.43	111.74	113.16
PROB:	0	0.67	0.33
RMSE:	2.48	1.37	1.27

MAX_MEAN: 4.87 MAX_MED: 5.05 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe
 CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008
 M4ID: 30004897

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.71 1.21 8
 sd: 1.05 0.261 14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 0.0538 -2.04 5.88 -1.76 7.26
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.1	179.78	190.1
PROB:	0.46	0.54	0
RMSE:	4.49	4.07	4.49

MAX_MEAN: 4.37 MAX_MED: 4.01 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.54

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30004830

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.83	1.86	0.331
sd:	4	1.18	0.146

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.83	1.86	0.331	3.64	5.87
sd:	4	1.18	0.146	676	2980

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.15	120.62	124.62
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.75	1.5	1.5

MAX_MEAN: 6.17 MAX_MED: 6.08 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyloctyl adipate
 CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14
 M4ID: 30004819

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.08 1.43 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.86 1.34 0.3 3.65 6.26
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.23	145.92	149.93
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.41	2.4	2.4

MAX_MEAN: 6.9 MAX_MED: 7.13 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Igepal CO-890
 CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08
 M4ID: 30005017

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.37 2.01 8
 sd: 1.95 0.104 11.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.63 2.03 8 2.32 14.6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.22	179.61	183.48
PROB:	0.19	0.71	0.1
RMSE:	4.64	4.1	4.1

MAX_MEAN: 6.12 MAX_MED: 7.07 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.81

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30005178

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.9	-0.131	0.546
sd:	1.12	0.381	0.174

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.9	-0.131	0.546	3.89	7.51
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.14	143.9	147.9
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.7	2.74	2.74

MAX_MEAN: 12.6 MAX_MED: 9.87 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol
 CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15
 M4ID: 30004602

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.2	1.92	7.71
sd:	1.41	0.0298	5.58

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.2	1.93	7.18	4.2	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.22	159.83	163.79
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.58	2.96	2.96

MAX_MEAN: 11 MAX_MED: 11.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Tromethamine
 CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15
 M4ID: 30004938

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 11 1.95 5.2
 sd: 2.79 0.0848 6.18

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.5 1.99 4.68 2.52 2.37
 sd: 101 0.972 13.8 9.11 114

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.77	186.62	190.61
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.75	4.69	4.68

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate
 CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12
 M4ID: 30005061

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.04	1.34	7.37
sd:	0.782	0.129	24.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.4	1.42	3.79	2.3	0.591
sd:	42.9	0.225	3.72	4.73	2.52

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.17	158.6	161.71
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	5.9	2.94	2.93

MAX_MEAN: 8.68 MAX_MED: 8.46 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30004734

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.46	1.6	2
sd:	1.12	0.157	0.936

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.3	2	1.48	2.31	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.31	140.16	141.89
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	4.32	2.19	2.08

MAX_MEAN: 7.97 MAX_MED: 6.63 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30005123

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.6	1.16	3.19
sd:	0.947	0.103	2.61

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.6	1.64	0.816	2.33	3.9
sd:	13.4	1.18	0.953	0.104	8.33

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.48	160.5	162.41
PROB:	0	0.72	0.28
RMSE:	5.83	3.04	2.97

MAX_MEAN: 8.32 MAX_MED: 9.27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyridate
 CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13
 M4ID: 30004748

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.22	1.54	1.73
sd:	1.63	0.152	0.782

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13	1.83	1.31	2.33	15.8
sd:	10.1	0.506	0.581	0.0263	22.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.56	124.15	127.01
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	4.68	1.66	1.63

MAX_MEAN: 8.25 MAX_MED: 9.88 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl
 CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21
 M4ID: 30004836

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.09 0.576 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.3 2.06 0.3 2.31 16.9
 sd: 41.2 8.28 0.588 0.0237 49.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.1	163.68	165.04
PROB:	0	0.66	0.34
RMSE:	6.23	3.4	3.23

MAX_MEAN: 8.84 MAX_MED: 6.15 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Buprofezin
 CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003
 M4ID: 30004518

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.34 1.77 4.29
 sd: 1.28 0.0644 2.47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 12.7 1.87 2.8 2.33 16
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	190.1	153.25	156.32
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	5.36	2.67	2.64

MAX_MEAN: 9.25 MAX_MED: 9.61 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-toluenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30005225

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.25	0.659	1.3
sd:	1.04	0.52	1.36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.2	1.77	0.729	2.02	1.23
sd:	113	7.29	1.49	2.25	1.85

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.64	166.51	169.8
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	4.73	3.56	3.51

MAX_MEAN: 5.22 MAX_MED: 5.45 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SR125047
 CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01
 M4ID: 30005120

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.37 1.76 1.67
 sd: 2.28 0.171 0.681

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.6 1.99 1.53 2.33 11.1
 sd: 10 0.364 0.604 0.0423 16.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.79	190.73	193.38
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	4.78	2.3	2.27

MAX_MEAN: 7.83 MAX_MED: 7.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanedio1

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30005066

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.13	1.99	8
sd:	2.39	0.0506	7.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.5	2.04	8	2.3	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.59	172.23	175.91
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	5.02	3.51	3.5

MAX_MEAN: 9.71 MAX_MED: 8.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate

CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16

M4ID: 30005057

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.1	1.48	2.43
sd:	1.34	0.163	0.876

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.1	1.73	1.83	2.4	2.41
sd:	25.1	0.699	0.868	0.419	7.83

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.22	150.89	153.81
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	6.09	2.54	2.43

MAX_MEAN: 11 MAX_MED: 10.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Zenarestat

CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24

M4ID: 30004953

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.8	1.94	8
sd:	2	0.0429	6.97

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.6	2.05	4.99	2.3	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.69	169.1	173.03
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.26	3.61	3.61

MAX_MEAN: 13.5 MAX_MED: 9.67 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline
 CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06
 M4ID: 30005187

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.1	1.57	0.878
sd:	4.6	0.464	0.44

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.7	1.62	0.848	2.82	3.13
sd:	13.5	1.16	0.665	9.62	63.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.97	150.23	154.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.14	2.61	2.61

MAX_MEAN: 9.74 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Trifluralin
 CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08
 M4ID: 30004825

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13 0.771 1.19
 sd: 1.44 0.171 0.572

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13 0.771 1.19 3.84 6.55
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.49	171.77	175.77
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10	3.85	3.85

MAX_MEAN: 14.4 MAX_MED: 14.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Vinclozolin
 CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22
 M4ID: 30004715

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.6 1.97 1.3
 sd: 2.84 0.156 0.359

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13.6 1.97 1.3 3.92 5.33
 sd: 2.84 0.156 0.36 1450 4760

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.38	126.58	130.58
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.88	1.68	1.68

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30004793

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12	1.14	2.08
sd:	0.733	0.0761	0.575

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.4	1.22	1.68	2.34	17.7
sd:	1.57	0.116	0.528	0.0139	8.39

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.42	140.77	141.65
PROB:	0	0.61	0.39
RMSE:	8.44	2.2	2.08

MAX_MEAN: 13.9 MAX_MED: 13.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diphenamid
 CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12
 M4ID: 30004821

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 14 1.79 0.591
 sd: 6.22 0.694 0.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14 1.79 0.591 2.98 9.23
 sd: 6.21 0.693 0.2 67.5 916

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.04	137.23	141.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.88	2.06	2.06

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate
 CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17
 M4ID: 30005080

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 14.4 1.1 1.46
 sd: 1.88 0.133 0.494

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.4 1.1 1.46 4.11 7.03
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	228.63	165.57	169.57
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.27	3.34	3.34

MAX_MEAN: 19.6 MAX_MED: 18.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30004974

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.4	2.23	0.971
sd:	11.9	0.688	0.347

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.4	2.23	0.971	3.45	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.16	134.42	138.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.19	1.92	1.92

MAX_MEAN: 8.87 MAX_MED: 8.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30004808

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.8	2.32	2.75
sd:	8.23	0.181	0.757

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.2	2.3	2.81	4.29	3.06
sd:	8.36	0.195	0.861	1070	1720

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.24	101.64	105.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.69	1.36	1.36

MAX_MEAN: 7.09 MAX_MED: 6.74 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Clomazone

CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09

M4ID: 30004488

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.3	2.01	7.52
sd:	3.16	0.0665	8.46

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.3	2.01	7.52	3.64	1.82
sd:	21.6	0.127	8.72	153	229

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.55	195.9	199.9
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.32	5.57	5.57

MAX_MEAN: 13.4 MAX_MED: 15.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine
 CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23
 M4ID: 30004834

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 14.4 1.28 1.3
 sd: 3.61 0.235 1.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.4 1.28 1.3 3.82 6.47
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.66	177.88	181.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.35	4	4

MAX_MEAN: 14.8 MAX_MED: 16.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzdine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30005084

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.6	1.74	1.72
sd:	3.61	0.192	0.687

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.5	2.02	1.53	2.31	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.32	157.78	160.12
PROB:	0	0.76	0.24
RMSE:	6.42	2.77	2.76

MAX_MEAN: 11.5 MAX_MED: 12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isophorone
 CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05
 M4ID: 30004972

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.9 2.09 2.7
 sd: 9.06 0.251 1.89

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.9 2.09 2.7 3.31 5.53
 sd: 9.07 0.251 1.89 885 4890

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.96	167.01	171.01
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.22	3.43	3.43

MAX_MEAN: 14.1 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30005086

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.6	1.86	2.41
sd:	3.21	0.11	1.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.9	2.09	1.94	2.34	7.6
sd:	35.1	0.529	0.914	0.0718	15.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.92	162.93	166.36
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	6.83	3.18	3.19

MAX_MEAN: 14.2 MAX_MED: 11.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline
 CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02
 M4ID: 30004879

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15 1.8 4.26
 sd: 1.24 0.0339 1.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 21.5 1.88 3.28 2.57 1.49
 sd: 47.6 0.294 2.4 1.21 10.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	280.42	199.93	203.73
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	7.79	2.66	2.67

MAX_MEAN: 14.9 MAX_MED: 14.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30005235

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.7	1.54	0.3
sd:	8.08	1.64	0.272

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.2	1.64	0.3	4	4.95
sd:	9.3	1.83	0.269	2390	6890

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.88	159.41	163.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.12	3.06	3.06

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 11.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal
 CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20
 M4ID: 30004837

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.8	2.21	0.798
sd:	16.3	0.883	0.397

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.8	2.21	0.798	4.1	4.49
sd:	16.3	0.883	0.397	2640	6570

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.15	167.5	171.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.07	3.29	3.29

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 11.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethalfluralin
 CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22
 M4ID: 30004547

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 14.9 1.36 1.72
 sd: 1.86 0.118 0.519

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.9 1.36 1.72 4.12 6.12
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	227.66	164.82	168.82
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.48	3.77	3.77

MAX_MEAN: 17.6 MAX_MED: 14.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol

CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02

M4ID: 30004831

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.8	1.97	0.792
sd:	7.2	0.404	0.222

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.8	1.97	0.792	4.3	4.15
sd:	7.2	0.404	0.222	2500	5090

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.49	147.28	151.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.15	2.45	2.45

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 13.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Finasteride
 CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22
 M4ID: 30004763

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.31e-08 2.8 0.323
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.68 -3.7 0.3 1.69 17.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.01	180.01	163.59
PROB:	0.01	0	0.99
RMSE:	4.01	4.01	3.07

MAX_MEAN: 4.51 MAX_MED: 4.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
 CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
 M4ID: 30005218

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.65 -3 3.34
 sd: 0.754 40.5 452

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.27 -3.17 1.12 2.12 18
 sd: 0.719 3.94 9.14 0.504 67.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.15	176.44	171.93
PROB:	0	0.1	0.9
RMSE:	6.21	3.91	3.46

MAX_MEAN: 7.96 MAX_MED: 7.41 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrofen
 CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22
 M4ID: 30004523

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.69	0.717	3.72
sd:	0.411	0.102	2.42

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.86	0.891	2.16	2.23	1.2
sd:	4.07	0.248	1.12	0.391	1.14

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.61	120.44	118.79
PROB:	0	0.3	0.7
RMSE:	4.6	1.5	1.44

MAX_MEAN: 6.8 MAX_MED: 6.34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Oxazepam
 CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15
 M4ID: 30005226

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.37	-2.65	4.25
sd:	0.488	3.45	304

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.4	-2.09	0.783	1.89	5
sd:	0.705	1.16	1.26	0.129	4.56

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.57	151.55	142.85
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	3.3	2.68	2.1

MAX_MEAN: 3.58 MAX_MED: 4.49 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Prednisone
 CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05
 M4ID: 30005044

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.15 -0.194 4.23
 sd: 0.616 1.55 36.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.88 1.01 8 1.58 2.02
 sd: 4.7 0.0579 27 0.366 1.26

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.78	152.3	138.03
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.2	2.57	1.99

MAX_MEAN: 6.2 MAX_MED: 6.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Disulfiram
 CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21
 M4ID: 30005076

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.6 1.62 8
 sd: 0.814 0.324 22.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.39 1.72 7.15 2 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.36	142.37	137.07
PROB:	0	0.07	0.93
RMSE:	3.13	2.5	1.91

MAX_MEAN: 6.11 MAX_MED: 6.76 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06
 M4ID: 30005115

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.2 -0.054 7.83
 sd: 0.688 2.9 420

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.44 0.24 1.04 1.92 18
 sd: 1.55 0.437 0.71 0.0225 10.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.91	162.72	140.56
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	4.04	3.22	2.02

MAX_MEAN: 7.02 MAX_MED: 6.43 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30005104

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.595	-3.61	7.42
sd:	0.479	411	3330

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.23	-3.37	1.54	-0.115	2.39
sd:	1.03	34.3	78.9	0.222	3.22

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.39	155.75	113.69
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.03	2.87	1.28

MAX_MEAN: 6.3 MAX_MED: 6.12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol
 CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19
 M4ID: 30005222

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.82	1.02	0.483
sd:	3.49	0.879	0.371

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10	1.38	0.535	2.31	5.69
sd:	2.98	0.507	0.174	0.0346	11.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.74	124.7	116.21
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	4.53	1.67	1.4

MAX_MEAN: 7.06 MAX_MED: 6.91 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenamiphos

CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08

M4ID: 30004801

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.72	0.882	3.34
sd:	0.63	0.101	1.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.46	0.915	2.81	2.3	17.7
sd:	0.618	0.0754	1.36	0.0123	62.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.39	148.96	141
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	6.16	2.57	2.21

MAX_MEAN: 9.91 MAX_MED: 8.93 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30004776

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.77	1.21	1.36
sd:	0.996	0.234	0.744

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.4	1.89	0.929	2.29	16.4
sd:	6.38	0.52	0.318	0.0175	31.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.34	125.99	122.33
PROB:	0	0.14	0.86
RMSE:	3.6	1.76	1.49

MAX_MEAN: 7.19 MAX_MED: 8.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30005238

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.31	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.9	1.83	0.3	2.26	8.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.48	131.89	131.64
PROB:	0	0.47	0.53
RMSE:	3.7	1.86	1.72

MAX_MEAN: 6.13 MAX_MED: 6.26 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid
 CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02
 M4ID: 30004807

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.65	1.15	7.32
sd:	0.81	0.228	10.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.45	1.55	1.39	1.99	18
sd:	13.3	1.19	2.17	0.0272	17.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.16	160.12	150.12
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	3.82	3.36	2.54

MAX_MEAN: 6.32 MAX_MED: 6.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanol
 CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05
 M4ID: 30005236

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.3 -2.76 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.64 1.22 0.3 2.26 5.63
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.16	137.34	131.73
PROB:	0	0.06	0.94
RMSE:	4.3	2.13	1.87

MAX_MEAN: 6.51 MAX_MED: 5.44 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30004850

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.1	-3.7	6.09
sd:	0.635	372	2270

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.8	-3.7	0.3	2.16	17.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.3	168.68	167.7
PROB:	0	0.38	0.62
RMSE:	4.73	3.36	3.13

MAX_MEAN: 5.68 MAX_MED: 5.23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Boscalid
 CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21
 M4ID: 30004812

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.38 -3.7 6.18
 sd: 0.537 429 2660

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.24 0.332 0.3 1.83 17.6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.2	162.17	146.73
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.72	3.23	2.46

MAX_MEAN: 4.88 MAX_MED: 5.59 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon
 CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10
 M4ID: 30004823

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.22 0.124 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.2 1.22 0.487 2.14 2.07
 sd: 7.58 1.37 0.456 0.207 1.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.76	147.03	146.72
PROB:	0	0.46	0.54
RMSE:	4.74	2.47	2.37

MAX_MEAN: 6.47 MAX_MED: 6.62 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin

CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20

M4ID: 30005149

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.42	1.06	6.14
sd:	0.722	0.0726	6.32

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.5	1.14	3.38	2.21	3.02
sd:	1.34	0.0575	1.05	0.0695	1.28

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.07	142.77	129.95
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	6.18	2.3	1.72

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 11.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butyl lactate
CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01
M4ID: 30005240

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.26	-3.68	0.3
sd:	0.842	2.19	0.491

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.91	-2.48	0.3	2.27	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.18	183.93	178.68
PROB:	0	0.07	0.93
RMSE:	4.44	2.14	1.89

MAX_MEAN: 5.53 MAX_MED: 5.51 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37
 CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23
 M4ID: 30004762

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.44 0.733 2.6
 sd: 0.747 0.201 1.64

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.13 1.03 1.43 1.98 8.18
 sd: 1.73 0.212 0.737 0.0384 4.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.13	151.22	129.73
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.75	2.83	1.67

MAX_MEAN: 6.41 MAX_MED: 6.25 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate
 CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10
 M4ID: 30004799

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.06 -3.7 6.84
 sd: 0.352 313 2140

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.95 1.03 8 1.49 2.05
 sd: 3.55 0.0788 14.7 0.313 1.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.6	132.87	123.53
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	2.22	1.86	1.65

MAX_MEAN: 4.21 MAX_MED: 4.96 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30004760

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.67	1.59	2.34
sd:	0.799	0.114	0.728

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.86	1.85	2.85	2.3	17.9
sd:	2.46	0.0864	0.93	0.00853	34

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.89	110.94	98.93
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.52	1.34	0.99

MAX_MEAN: 8.01 MAX_MED: 8.11 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl
 CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19
 M4ID: 30005198

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.22 0.385 1.14
 sd: 1.18 0.477 0.904

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 17.2 1.56 0.637 1.96 8.06
 sd: 10.4 0.82 0.26 0.0317 3.47

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.9	175.38	147.31
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	5.84	4.22	2.38

MAX_MEAN: 9.61 MAX_MED: 10.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Mifepristone
 CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01
 M4ID: 30004832

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 10 -1.11 0.633
 sd: 0.756 0.415 0.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 18.1 0.182 0.378 2.02 1.47
 sd: 4.36 0.609 0.0885 0.119 0.575

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.05	155.67	133.4
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	8.95	2.89	1.78

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 12.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Amitraz

CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08

M4ID: 30004777

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.49	0.923	2.56
sd:	0.693	0.116	1.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.8	1.1	1.91	2.19	0.833
sd:	10.7	0.189	0.985	0.727	0.76

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	210.39	149.57	148.06
PROB:	0	0.32	0.68
RMSE:	7.29	2.45	2.26

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Carbosulfan
 CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15
 M4ID: 30004842

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 11.3 0.81 1.65
 sd: 0.967 0.12 0.665

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 17.7 1.16 0.99 2.24 2.07
 sd: 6.88 0.354 0.387 0.138 1.01

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.25	152.85	142.99
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	8.46	2.53	2

MAX_MEAN: 12.9 MAX_MED: 14.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol
 CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05
 M4ID: 30004804

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.56 1.35 3.25
 sd: 0.666 0.0886 1.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.9 1.71 1.69 2.3 17.2
 sd: 8.58 0.356 0.736 0.0102 95.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.76	130.1	124.82
PROB:	0	0.07	0.93
RMSE:	6.1	2	1.57

MAX_MEAN: 11.5 MAX_MED: 11.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol
 CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24
 M4ID: 30005169

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.58	0.385	1.5
sd:	1.23	0.517	1.46

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.8	1.44	0.49	1.98	12.1
sd:	35.9	4.24	0.972	0.0337	10.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.01	201.51	189.56
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.87	7.61	5.66

MAX_MEAN: 8.94 MAX_MED: 9.02 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol

CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10

M4ID: 30005159 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.86	-3.69	6.52
sd:	1.29	400	2630

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.4	1.15	2.03	1.7	7.79
sd:	17.7	0.691	3.23	0.122	12.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.27	219.45	214.34
PROB:	0.37	0.05	0.59
RMSE:	8.54	8.76	7.82

MAX_MEAN: 8.5 MAX_MED: 8.25 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 0.63

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30004660

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.53	1.25	8
sd:	2.4	0.161	14.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.2	1.34	7.96	1.96	18
sd:	2.14	0.131	24.7	0.0229	9.45

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	210.23	207.86	186.86
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	8.04	7.14	4.6

MAX_MEAN: 15.3 MAX_MED: 11.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: p-Cresol
 CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07
 M4ID: 30005234

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.6 0.735 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.8 0.933 0.3 2.3 4.31
 sd: 7.67 1.47 0.158 0.0541 3.99

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.82	159.79	152.41
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	7.82	2.88	2.49

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 12 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 31 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30004686

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.7	1.59	1.96
sd:	3.2	0.174	0.855

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	36.8	2.06	1.43	2.31	12.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	226.7	186.7	189.41
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	10.64	5.08	4.72

MAX_MEAN: 20.9 MAX_MED: 19.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol
 CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15
 M4ID: 30004746

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15 1.7 2.15
 sd: 1.22 0.0532 0.678

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15 1.7 2.15 4.15 6.16
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	211.35	132.69	136.69
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.98	1.98	1.98

MAX_MEAN: 16.2 MAX_MED: 17.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isopropalin
 CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12
 M4ID: 30004917

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.4 1.03 3.27
 sd: 0.907 0.0612 1.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.4 1.03 3.27 4.29 6.01
 sd: 0.907 0.0612 1.41 61200 184000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.43	162.46	166.46
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.91	3.26	3.26

MAX_MEAN: 16.9 MAX_MED: 17.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pendimethalin
CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20
M4ID: 30004477

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.3	1.01	4.34
sd:	1.26	0.0686	3.79

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.3	1.01	4.34	3.46	5.72
sd:	1.26	0.0686	3.8	502	2440

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	242.72	186.47	190.47
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.7	4.81	4.81

MAX_MEAN: 19.1 MAX_MED: 16.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate
 CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07
 M4ID: 30005114

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15	1.95	4.43
sd:	2.4	0.0469	2.69

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.5	2	3.9	2.34	15.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.01	164.98	168.83
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	6.22	3.21	3.19

MAX_MEAN: 12.8 MAX_MED: 15.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline
 CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01
 M4ID: 30004544

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.3	1.94	5.42
sd:	0.95	0.015	1.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.9	1.99	4.5	2.33	18
sd:	6.9	0.0552	0.928	0.00975	16.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.66	118.82	121.77
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	7.12	1.48	1.46

MAX_MEAN: 17.2 MAX_MED: 16.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane
 CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16
 M4ID: 30005201

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.5 1.12 1.75
 sd: 0.943 0.0724 0.598

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 16.5 1.12 1.75 4.04 5.76
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	235.48	150.17	154.17
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.08	2.7	2.7

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 17.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: HMR1426
 CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04
 M4ID: 30005213

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 17 1.91 5.12
 sd: 1.43 0.0273 1.97

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 21.6 1.96 4.13 2.41 5.82
 sd: 32.7 0.317 4.17 0.244 30.3

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	210.5	160.8	164.72
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.82	3.2	3.2

MAX_MEAN: 16.8 MAX_MED: 16.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal

CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09

M4ID: 30004992

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.4	1.88	2.48
sd:	3.75	0.103	1.11

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.4	1.88	2.48	3.33	6.74
sd:	3.75	0.103	1.11	838	5570

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	204.16	161.28	165.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.01	3.1	3.1

MAX_MEAN: 13.8 MAX_MED: 15.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol
 CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06
 M4ID: 30004995

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	58.9	-3.7	6.02
sd:	3.08	224	1350

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	76.6	-1.09	8	2.24	0.741
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	341.44	264.67	275.45
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	62.41	16.9	23.56

MAX_MEAN: 78.6 MAX_MED: 74.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 40 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Biphenyl

CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06

M4ID: 30005043

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	92.6	1.9	4.08
sd:	4.64	0.0242	0.572

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	124	1.96	3.67	2.33	16.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	303.76	209.5	211.66
PROB:	0	0.75	0.25
RMSE:	41.55	8.99	8.2

MAX_MEAN: 91.3 MAX_MED: 89.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cupferron
 CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16
 M4ID: 30005153

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	107	1.86	3.1
sd:	5.66	0.0198	0.64

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	130	1.92	2.72	2.34	18
sd:	15.1	0.0392	0.476	0.00661	6.08

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	314.98	202.3	202.35
PROB:	0	0.51	0.49
RMSE:	46.71	6.15	5.76

MAX_MEAN: 101 MAX_MED: 101 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene

CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10

M4ID: 30005135

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	26	1.06	8
sd:	1.61	0.0718	9.08

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.1	1.1	5.34	2.48	2.61
sd:	3.99	0.0714	2.96	0.251	4.28

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	267.65	188.16	189.26
PROB:	0	0.63	0.37
RMSE:	19.34	4.73	4.5

MAX_MEAN: 30.2 MAX_MED: 30.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Endrin
 CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15
 M4ID: 30004722

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 28.2 0.39 1.27
 sd: 1.46 0.0898 0.266

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 28.2 0.39 1.27 3.32 7.78
 sd: 1.46 0.0898 0.266 959 7270

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	278.25	173.91	177.91
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	22.21	3.76	3.76

MAX_MEAN: 30.5 MAX_MED: 32.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30004679

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.8	0.339	2.31
sd:	1.22	0.0826	0.633

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30.8	0.339	2.31	3.68	9.47
sd:	1.22	0.0826	0.633	97900	684000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	285.67	186.1	190.1
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	25.05	4.5	4.5

MAX_MEAN: 33.4 MAX_MED: 34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine

CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06

M4ID: 30005091

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.8	1.04	2.44
sd:	1.14	0.053	1.02

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.8	1.04	2.44	2.89	16.1
sd:	1.14	0.053	1.02	397	10400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	250.79	167.21	171.21
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	14.4	3.39	3.39

MAX_MEAN: 24.9 MAX_MED: 24.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline

CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10

M4ID: 30005087

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	72.6	1.99	4.78
sd:	2.36	0.0102	0.738

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	103	2.06	4.11	2.33	18
sd:	7.81	0.0104	0.458	0.00516	6.01

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	273.07	165.14	167.44
PROB:	0	0.76	0.24
RMSE:	27.44	3.82	3.79

MAX_MEAN: 74.6 MAX_MED: 70.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol
 CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03
 M4ID: 30004542

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 25.4 1.75 3.92
 sd: 1.77 0.0349 1.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 33.8 1.85 2.78 2.33 17.7
 sd: 21.2 0.235 1.53 0.0206 26.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.02	166.75	167.19
PROB:	0	0.56	0.44
RMSE:	13.1	3.29	3.11

MAX_MEAN: 25.9 MAX_MED: 25.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dibenzofuran
 CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14
 M4ID: 30004483

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	60.7	1.89	5.47
sd:	4.22	0.0182	1.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	81	1.94	4.81	2.33	17.3
sd:	25.1	0.0587	1.27	0.0163	15.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	279.3	193.83	194.84
PROB:	0	0.62	0.38
RMSE:	26.87	5.63	5.54

MAX_MEAN: 56.8 MAX_MED: 58.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Flavone

CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11

M4ID: 30004702

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	22.1	1.68	2.93
sd:	2.65	0.0738	1.38

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	55.6	1.9	2.36	2.15	1.26
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.12	206.77	208.46
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	21.78	15.08	15.41

MAX_MEAN: 46.1 MAX_MED: 23.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: EPN
 CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010
 M4ID: 30004895

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 33.3 1.18 2.66
 sd: 1.29 0.0348 0.592

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 33.3 1.18 2.66 3.23 8.45
 sd: 1.29 0.0348 0.592 759 6900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	276.92	171.85	175.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	22.47	3.59	3.59

MAX_MEAN: 38.4 MAX_MED: 38.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triphenylethylene

CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06

M4ID: 30004611

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	99.1	0.616	0.833
sd:	8.99	0.161	0.191

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	99.1	0.616	0.833	3.36	17.5
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	347.19	244.83	248.83
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	70.59	12.41	12.41

MAX_MEAN: 99.3 MAX_MED: 101 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24

M4ID: 30004761

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	134	1.63	2.43
sd:	4.44	0.0285	0.215

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	134	1.63	2.43	3.43	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	343.8	201.5	205.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	71.52	5.98	5.98

MAX_MEAN: 127 MAX_MED: 128 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben
 CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11
 M4ID: 30004966

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.6	1.79	2.93
sd:	2.07	0.0338	0.675

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	38.7	1.86	2.41	2.34	17.9
sd:	12.7	0.134	0.702	0.0104	14.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	248.62	163.49	165.99
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	14.97	3.11	3.05

MAX_MEAN: 30.2 MAX_MED: 29.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine
 CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09
 M4ID: 30004704

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 39.5 0.983 3.66
 sd: 1.86 0.036 1.38

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 39.5 0.983 3.66 3.26 10.1
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	289.16	209.82	213.82
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	27.61	8.26	8.26

MAX_MEAN: 45.9 MAX_MED: 45.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethion
 CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19
 M4ID: 30005126

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 27.1 1.06 1.29
 sd: 2.74 0.101 0.388

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 41.2 1.42 0.918 2.45 1.48
 sd: 33.7 0.67 0.362 0.335 1.66

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	263.87	172.84	173.84
PROB:	0	0.62	0.38
RMSE:	17.95	3.62	3.67

MAX_MEAN: 26.7 MAX_MED: 28.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Troclosesene
 CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19
 M4ID: 30004838

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 20.4 1.34 1.63
 sd: 2.01 0.0923 0.438

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 20.4 1.34 1.63 4.02 8.04
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	242.86	164.32	168.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13	3.39	3.39

MAX_MEAN: 22.3 MAX_MED: 22.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine
 CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08
 M4ID: 30005041

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 25.3 1.96 6.92
 sd: 2.62 0.0209 2.52

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 25.3 1.96 6.92 3.89 14
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	222.35	178.19	182.19
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.1	4.11	4.11

MAX_MEAN: 23.2 MAX_MED: 25.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30005009

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	49.7	1.94	7.17
sd:	2.36	0.00985	1.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	72	2	5.2	2.32	17.7
sd:	7.92	0.0172	0.682	0.00625	7.85

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	262.57	176.22	179.11
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	21.09	3.85	3.82

MAX_MEAN: 51.8 MAX_MED: 48.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30004792

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	59.6	0.945	2.46
sd:	2.22	0.0347	0.404

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	106	1.07	2.01	2.48	0.315
sd:	296	0.185	0.405	7.58	1.18

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	320.5	214.77	216.02
PROB:	0	0.65	0.35
RMSE:	46.15	9.01	8.1

MAX_MEAN: 69.5 MAX_MED: 70.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone
 CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14
 M4ID: 30004843

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 69.1 0.189 1.13
 sd: 1.77 0.0635 0.211

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 69.1 0.189 1.13 3.79 9.56
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.98	198.8	202.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	54.79	5.69	5.69

MAX_MEAN: 71 MAX_MED: 70 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinyll acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30004962

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	58.5	1.92	5.65
sd:	2.19	0.0153	1.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	58.5	1.92	5.65	4.29	4.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	275.58	183.15	187.15
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	25.31	4.38	4.38

MAX_MEAN: 57.8 MAX_MED: 58.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30004741

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	70.8	0.996	1.41
sd:	2.06	0.0364	0.143

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	70.8	0.996	1.41	3.06	11
sd:	2.06	0.0364	0.143	307	4450

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	323.34	169.86	173.86
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	47.91	3.75	3.75

MAX_MEAN: 74.6 MAX_MED: 75.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol

CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09

M4ID: 30004944

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	102	1.32	2.36
sd:	3.7	0.0324	0.348

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	102	1.32	2.36	3.9	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	336.94	225.88	229.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	62.25	11.7	11.7

MAX_MEAN: 110 MAX_MED: 107 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30005202

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	38.9	1.87	3.34
sd:	2.27	0.0288	0.673

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	38.9	1.87	3.34	4.27	16.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	252.06	165.17	169.17
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	16.64	3.39	3.39

MAX_MEAN: 35.9 MAX_MED: 37.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30005154

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	273	1.91	0.973
sd:	27.1	0.0958	0.0747

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	273	1.91	0.973	3.62	17.2
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	362.44	234.64	238.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	97.88	11.86	11.86

MAX_MEAN: 209 MAX_MED: 204 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (E)-Anethole
 CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05
 M4ID: 30005164

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 98.4 1.94 1.16
 sd: 14.4 0.119 0.145

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 98.4 1.94 1.16 3.24 18
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	298.04	193.55	197.55
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	34.14	5.72	5.72

MAX_MEAN: 70.1 MAX_MED: 71.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Azobenzene

CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12

M4ID: 30005181

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	138	1.53	1.62
sd:	8.74	0.053	0.167

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	138	1.53	1.62	4.3	9.95
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	348.4	230.75	234.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	76.63	11.58	11.58

MAX_MEAN: 137 MAX_MED: 145 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30005037

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	117	1.94	1.43
sd:	15.8	0.0958	0.204

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	117	1.94	1.43	2.81	17.9
sd:	15.8	0.0958	0.204	320	10000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	307.19	213.12	217.12
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	40.27	8.29	8.28

MAX_MEAN: 83.2 MAX_MED: 90.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol

CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22

M4ID: 30005195

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	118	1.44	1.16
sd:	6	0.0585	0.115

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	118	1.44	1.16	4.29	14.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	338.19	198.54	202.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	62.69	5.69	5.69

MAX_MEAN: 107 MAX_MED: 105 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Carbofuran
 CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06
 M4ID: 30004875

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 52.5 2.07 1.61
 sd: 20.7 0.234 0.53

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 52.5 2.07 1.61 4.01 17.9
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	256.2	198.15	202.15
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	18.06	6.3	6.3

MAX_MEAN: 40.8 MAX_MED: 37.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol
 CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22
 M4ID: 30005147

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 32.1 1.66 0.848
 sd: 8.98 0.339 0.27

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 32.4 1.65 0.885 3.9 0.834
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	250.56	171.59	175.42
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	14.44	3.75	3.74

MAX_MEAN: 23.4 MAX_MED: 23.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30005231

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	26.2	1.26	0.849
sd:	5.7	0.275	0.389

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	32.6	1.53	0.718	2.34	18
sd:	12.2	0.503	0.275	0.0189	10.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.18	175.82	177.54
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	14.91	3.83	3.67

MAX_MEAN: 22.8 MAX_MED: 23 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Nitrilotriacetic acid
 CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
 M4ID: 30005219

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	80.3	1.68	0.878
sd:	15.9	0.222	0.175

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	81.7	1.69	0.902	2.36	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	302.5	191.11	193.25
PROB:	0	0.74	0.26
RMSE:	34.63	5.15	5.09

MAX_MEAN: 60.1 MAX_MED: 57.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenothiazine

CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19

M4ID: 30005150

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	80	1.81	1.01
sd:	10.1	0.123	0.114

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	80	1.81	1.01	4.05	14.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	294.9	165.6	169.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	31.17	3.45	3.45

MAX_MEAN: 58.7 MAX_MED: 60.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Picloram

CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18

M4ID: 30004599

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	75.1	1.56	1.23
sd:	7.92	0.113	0.213

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	96.1	1.74	1.12	2.34	16.9
sd:	26.6	0.231	0.19	0.0095	8.88

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	307.23	207.39	208.42
PROB:	0	0.63	0.37
RMSE:	38.35	6.93	6.54

MAX_MEAN: 65.5 MAX_MED: 66.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30005127

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.5	1.53	1.04
sd:	5.36	0.169	0.189

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.5	1.53	1.04	3.18	7.87
sd:	5.36	0.169	0.189	574	5180

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	263.11	161.48	165.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	18.1	3.24	3.24

MAX_MEAN: 30.3 MAX_MED: 30.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide
 CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11
 M4ID: 30004822

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	66	2.15	3.12
sd:	14.3	0.0832	0.817

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	66	2.15	3.12	3.41	8.85
sd:	14.3	0.0833	0.817	4380	34900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	233.49	185.27	189.27
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	15.73	5.43	5.43

MAX_MEAN: 43.8 MAX_MED: 49.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benzophenone

CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18

M4ID: 30005151

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	115	1.71	0.993
sd:	6.43	0.0607	0.0586

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	115	1.71	0.993	3.36	17.2
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	322.41	168.81	172.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	48.99	3.94	3.94

MAX_MEAN: 93.6 MAX_MED: 93.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30005007

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	67.7	1.86	1.81
sd:	6.31	0.0586	0.295

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67.7	1.86	1.81	3.68	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.92	184.19	188.19
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	27.51	4.33	4.33

MAX_MEAN: 58 MAX_MED: 57 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol
 CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22
 M4ID: 30005171

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 62.4 1.62 1.06
 sd: 9.31 0.155 0.194

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 66.9 1.67 1.05 2.37 13
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	290.07	189.04	189.9
PROB:	0	0.61	0.39
RMSE:	28.45	4.88	4.65

MAX_MEAN: 48.5 MAX_MED: 47.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Disulfoton

CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23

M4ID: 30004810

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	22.4	1.72	1.34
sd:	3.5	0.129	0.366

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	26.6	1.83	1.36	2.35	16.1
sd:	8.17	0.202	0.318	0.0184	10.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	228.8	151.15	153.03
PROB:	0	0.72	0.28
RMSE:	10.44	2.61	2.49

MAX_MEAN: 20 MAX_MED: 20.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane
 CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18
 M4ID: 30004863

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 40 2 4.24
 sd: 6.76 0.0643 2.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 40.1 2 4.24 3.11 8.66
 sd: 6.76 0.0643 2.01 987 10600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	247.66	210.09	214.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	15.64	6.6	6.6

MAX_MEAN: 38.8 MAX_MED: 37.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Diphenolic acid
 CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13
 M4ID: 30004580

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 75.3 2 1.71
 sd: 9.42 0.0717 0.256

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 75.3 2 1.71 4.26 6.26
 sd: 9.42 0.0717 0.256 106000 336000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	275.43	170.99	174.99
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	24.39	3.75	3.75

MAX_MEAN: 56 MAX_MED: 58.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Phenolphthalin

CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05

M4ID: 30004540

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	93.7	2.01	2.65
sd:	10.9	0.0501	0.589

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	101	2.04	2.62	2.39	13.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.59	170.04	173.82
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	30.49	3.65	3.61

MAX_MEAN: 77.6 MAX_MED: 79.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Warfarin
 CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07
 M4ID: 30005210

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 21.6 1.94 1.03
 sd: 5.8 0.25 0.283

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 21.6 1.94 1.03 3.3 7.53
 sd: 5.8 0.25 0.283 779 5800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	211.11	144.43	148.43
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.79	2.27	2.27

MAX_MEAN: 15.5 MAX_MED: 14.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane

CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12

M4ID: 30004845

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.3	2.02	1.35
sd:	6.84	0.137	0.317

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.3	2.02	1.35	3.49	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	233.54	163.81	167.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.66	3.13	3.13

MAX_MEAN: 26.8 MAX_MED: 25.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cypermethrin
 CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09
 M4ID: 30004920

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 70.6 1.8 0.997
 sd: 13.4 0.191 0.157

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 70.6 1.8 0.997 3.49 7.62
 sd: 13.4 0.191 0.157 2210 14200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	289.04	180.48	184.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	28.17	4.06	4.06

MAX_MEAN: 53.3 MAX_MED: 55.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether
 CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09
 M4ID: 30004824

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 77.6 1.85 1.19
 sd: 9.72 0.105 0.155

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 77.6 1.85 1.19 2.95 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	291.65	183.63	187.63
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	30.3	4.54	4.54

MAX_MEAN: 60.7 MAX_MED: 63.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite
 CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17
 M4ID: 30004672

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	25.1	1.9	2.7
sd:	3.01	0.0586	0.892

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.1	1.96	2.53	2.35	13.8
sd:	15.6	0.162	0.781	0.0188	17.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	226.04	153.24	156.43
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	10.62	2.63	2.58

MAX_MEAN: 23.3 MAX_MED: 22.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30005199

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	94.5	1.27	0.878
sd:	6.66	0.0957	0.104

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	94.5	1.27	0.878	2.89	15.9
sd:	6.66	0.0957	0.104	489	12700

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	328.81	192.18	196.18
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	52.76	5.11	5.11

MAX_MEAN: 87.4 MAX_MED: 84.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30005106

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	36.2	1.75	1.64
sd:	3.42	0.0697	0.298

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	44	1.86	1.57	2.34	17.9
sd:	12.8	0.162	0.288	0.0107	11.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	255.74	165.95	167.67
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	16.77	3.52	3.28

MAX_MEAN: 32.3 MAX_MED: 34.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dinotefuran
 CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08
 M4ID: 30004609

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 53.1 2.8 1.27
 sd: 437 3.92 1.34

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 46.5 -0.475 8 -0.224 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	254.15	250.07	264.15
PROB:	0.12	0.88	0
RMSE:	27.17	26.56	27.16

MAX_MEAN: 48.5 MAX_MED: 69.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.88

FLAGS: 11; 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30004778

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.1	2.1	1.62
sd:	17.4	0.35	0.917

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.1	2.05	2.01	2.35	17.9
sd:	22.1	0.289	1.01	0.0243	33.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	216.74	142.54	146.19
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	9.32	2.2	2.16

MAX_MEAN: 21.9 MAX_MED: 20.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30004647

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	24.9	2.08	1.22
sd:	12	0.362	0.449

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.9	2.08	1.22	3.12	7.3
sd:	12	0.362	0.449	323	2810

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.9	152.29	156.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.74	2.61	2.61

MAX_MEAN: 17.5 MAX_MED: 15.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Penoxsulam
 CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18
 M4ID: 30005175

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 69.5 1.31 1.01
 sd: 4.27 0.0882 0.133

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 77.7 1.43 0.912 2.36 18
 sd: 13.1 0.213 0.167 0.0139 8.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.07	180.9	182.62
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	38.84	4.25	4.15

MAX_MEAN: 62 MAX_MED: 61.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30004493

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.5	1.92	1.77
sd:	5.36	0.101	0.508

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	33.1	1.94	1.83	2.37	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	236.39	160.65	164.24
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	12.13	3.27	3.24

MAX_MEAN: 25.5 MAX_MED: 26.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone
 CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12
 M4ID: 30005109

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 25.8 2.01 1.92
 sd: 5.56 0.118 0.641

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 25.8 2.01 1.92 3.87 4.73
 sd: 5.56 0.118 0.64 625 1880

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	216.74	154.88	158.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.87	2.7	2.7

MAX_MEAN: 20.5 MAX_MED: 21.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30004790

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	64.5	2.08	2.84
sd:	7.01	0.0462	0.478

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	64.5	2.08	2.84	3.96	6.13
sd:	7.01	0.0462	0.478	9910	36600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.67	159.75	163.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	18.07	3.41	3.41

MAX_MEAN: 48.6 MAX_MED: 52.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone

CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22

M4ID: 30005075

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	26	1.96	1.44
sd:	4.96	0.132	0.305

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	26	1.96	1.44	3.66	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.38	146.52	150.52
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.21	2.48	2.48

MAX_MEAN: 20.1 MAX_MED: 21.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone
 CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20
 M4ID: 30004957

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 76.8 1.96 2.15
 sd: 7.19 0.0456 0.302

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 89 2.01 2.04 2.36 16.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	281.84	173.54	176.8
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	27.74	3.95	3.9

MAX_MEAN: 65.7 MAX_MED: 64.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Zamifenacin
 CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24
 M4ID: 30005193

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 23.9 1.54 0.984
 sd: 6.82 0.33 0.383

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 23.9 1.54 0.984 4.08 17.6
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.32	172.99	176.99
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.3	3.87	3.87

MAX_MEAN: 19.8 MAX_MED: 19.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SSR150106

CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15

M4ID: 30005130

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	21.9	2.39	1.21
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.3	2.3	1.14	3.58	5.58
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.55	139.96	144.18
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	5.27	2.64	2.78

MAX_MEAN: 12.9 MAX_MED: 16.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate

CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05

M4ID: 30004684

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.6	2.1	1.27
sd:	25.9	0.546	0.735

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	41	2.15	1.32	2.4	9.65
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	231.15	179.93	183.76
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	11.62	4.19	4.2

MAX_MEAN: 25.4 MAX_MED: 21.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30005208

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	29.5	1.28	1.14
sd:	2.97	0.125	0.264

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	29.5	1.28	1.14	2.84	17.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	262	165.53	169.53
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	17.47	3.29	3.29

MAX_MEAN: 26.8 MAX_MED: 27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol

CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08

M4ID: 30004633

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	45.2	-3.64	7.46
sd:	8.02	333	2630

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	75	-3.7	1.76	1.43	2.81
sd:	2.51	21	38.2	0.0435	0.441

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.74	315.69	234.78
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	55.59	37.53	9.91

MAX_MEAN: 79 MAX_MED: 78.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 49 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
 CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
 M4ID: 30005099

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	70.7	0.62	8
sd:	8.53	0.0539	16.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	112	0.796	2.25	1.92	7.11
sd:	8.59	0.05	0.412	0.019	2.94

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	333.27	301.64	238.65
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	59.42	33.46	11.26

MAX_MEAN: 114 MAX_MED: 114 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Catechol

CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18

M4ID: 30004551

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.2	1.32	3.19
sd:	1.96	0.0355	0.789

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	40.1	1.38	2.49	2.32	17.9
sd:	2.65	0.045	0.468	0.00601	5.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	277.23	182.65	169.25
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	23.1	4.39	3.29

MAX_MEAN: 43.8 MAX_MED: 44.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: o,p'-DDD

CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19

M4ID: 30004982

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	64.5	0.816	2.44
sd:	2.44	0.0521	0.464

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	72.5	0.886	1.93	2.11	6.1
sd:	3.26	0.0462	0.269	0.0236	1.11

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	317.29	242.48	188.15
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	43.93	19.27	4.46

MAX_MEAN: 68.5 MAX_MED: 69.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17

M4ID: 30004744

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.9	0.782	3.63
sd:	1.94	0.0636	1.02

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	37.3	0.871	2.72	2.07	7.14
sd:	3.55	0.0563	0.619	0.034	3.52

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	277.28	222.18	186.7
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	22.71	11.93	4.86

MAX_MEAN: 37.9 MAX_MED: 41.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone
 CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18
 M4ID: 30004767

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	77.2	0.00985	1.73
sd:	4.61	0.0944	0.822

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	116	0.424	0.779	2.06	1.58
sd:	21.9	0.249	0.162	0.0941	0.327

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	340.45	263.25	218.08
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	62.7	17.82	7.52

MAX_MEAN: 89.3 MAX_MED: 90 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Endosulfan

CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03

M4ID: 30004710

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30	1.04	3.89
sd:	1.24	0.0276	1.56

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	44.3	1.14	2.62	2.47	0.743
sd:	19	0.0739	0.496	0.458	0.642

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	274.39	172.06	163.76
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	21.36	3.62	3.18

MAX_MEAN: 33.4 MAX_MED: 34 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Ethoxyquin
 CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19
 M4ID: 30005078

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.8	1.25	3.07
sd:	1.24	0.0629	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.2	1.31	2.46	2.32	18
sd:	2.19	0.0873	0.893	0.0149	14.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.41	173.42	171.88
PROB:	0	0.32	0.68
RMSE:	11.48	4.01	3.52

MAX_MEAN: 19.1 MAX_MED: 19.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30004656

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	66.4	-0.91	7.51
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	75.5	-0.301	1.04	2.6	1.75
sd:	5.39	0.135	0.237	0.22	1.26

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	339.37	234.89	227.28
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	60.63	10.07	8.42

MAX_MEAN: 72.4 MAX_MED: 77.7 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol

CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03

M4ID: 30004854

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	45.1	0.329	3.97
sd:	10.7	0.574	5.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	92.3	0.713	1.59	1.88	18
sd:	6.78	0.083	0.318	0.0127	6.09

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	319.19	304.72	233.33
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	47.49	32.81	9.81

MAX_MEAN: 92.2 MAX_MED: 89 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Propyl gallate

CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12

M4ID: 30005205

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	40.8	1.41	2.56
sd:	3.4	0.0806	0.666

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	52.6	1.58	1.83	2.31	8.85
sd:	13.7	0.182	0.576	0.0219	24.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	279.68	209.67	203.98
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	24.56	7.26	5.88

MAX_MEAN: 45 MAX_MED: 44.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Quercetin

CHID: 21218 CASRN: 117-39-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H15

M4ID: 30005058

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	43.7	1.19	5.86
sd:	1.4	0.023	0.979

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	71.5	1.26	5.08	2.38	0.551
sd:	21.4	0.0194	0.741	0.468	0.25

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	295.78	177.51	158.9
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	30.9	4.53	2.96

MAX_MEAN: 52.6 MAX_MED: 52.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A
 CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15
 M4ID: 30004986

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 46.2 2.8 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 61.1 0.967 8 1.69 17.9
 sd: 5.32 0.0936 23.5 0.0186 23.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	282.09	288.09	241.77
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	27.16	27.16	11.35

MAX_MEAN: 60.9 MAX_MED: 61.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30004827

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	56.6	-0.288	1.37
sd:	3.04	0.182	0.45

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67.7	-0.107	0.938	2.03	5.59
sd:	4.08	0.115	0.171	0.0193	1.74

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	323.23	253.79	206.72
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	46.97	17.58	6.74

MAX_MEAN: 67.3 MAX_MED: 70.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5alpha-Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30004798

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	87.7	-0.188	1.61
sd:	2.71	0.0929	0.464

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	100	-0.0952	1.19	2.37	1.52
sd:	3.36	0.0456	0.125	0.0427	0.261

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	350.74	240.87	192.42
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	73.51	13.17	5.07

MAX_MEAN: 96.4 MAX_MED: 94.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Progesterone

CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06

M4ID: 30004947

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.5	0.994	8
sd:	2.46	0.0604	16.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.1	1.1	2.79	1.96	15.3
sd:	3.46	0.0975	1.36	0.0264	8.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.17	225.66	198.02
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	12.55	10.32	5.57

MAX_MEAN: 21.5 MAX_MED: 22.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Bisphenol B
 CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10
 M4ID: 30004487

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 61 -0.945 7.41
 sd: 11.9 24.8 3320

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 103 -0.493 1.4 1.71 18
 sd: 3.79 0.0911 0.223 0.00627 7.41

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	341.79	327.6	234.77
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	66.21	46.89	9.63

MAX_MEAN: 109 MAX_MED: 110 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol
 CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11
 M4ID: 30004846

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 37.4 -0.906 6.07
 sd: 8.21 4.34 281

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 71.2 -0.129 1.01 1.74 18
 sd: 6.53 0.151 0.323 0.0272 11.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	316.6	306.65	254.49
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	43.3	33.38	15.87

MAX_MEAN: 70.1 MAX_MED: 69.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30004772

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	81.9	1.58	3.45
sd:	1.88	0.0194	0.286

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	89.1	1.62	2.98	2.36	16.3
sd:	3.4	0.0247	0.29	0.00779	3.08

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	319.42	180.38	175.42
PROB:	0	0.08	0.92
RMSE:	47.65	5.16	4.24

MAX_MEAN: 87.4 MAX_MED: 82.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol

CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10

M4ID: 30004991

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	75.1	1.38	3.57
sd:	3.34	0.0338	0.919

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	109	1.53	2.34	2.41	1.44
sd:	76.6	0.186	0.558	0.356	2.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	321.66	220.06	216.48
PROB:	0	0.14	0.86
RMSE:	48.95	9.12	7.47

MAX_MEAN: 88.9 MAX_MED: 88.8 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Dodecylphenol
 CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19
 M4ID: 30004814

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	40	-0.655	3.19
sd:	7.14	1.56	13.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	70.3	-0.0689	1.42	1.78	4.11
sd:	4.37	0.0828	0.415	0.0401	1.05

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	314.29	294.5	235.64
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	42.07	27.41	11.52

MAX_MEAN: 74.5 MAX_MED: 73.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Fenhexamid

CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20

M4ID: 30005125

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	73.3	1.25	3.74
sd:	5.45	0.0388	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	86.8	1.3	2.85	2.01	18
sd:	4.99	0.029	0.435	0.0068	7.37

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	313.5	266.07	204.04
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	44.32	24	7.07

MAX_MEAN: 89.7 MAX_MED: 93.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen
 CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21
 M4ID: 30004692

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 38.9 1.15 1.96
 sd: 1.5 0.0346 0.25

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 42.1 1.2 1.68 2.39 6.1
 sd: 1.59 0.0353 0.196 0.0242 1.77

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.59	161.47	144.56
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	25.48	3.22	2.33

MAX_MEAN: 40.5 MAX_MED: 40 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30004727

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.7	0.792	2.3
sd:	6.14	0.187	1.02

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	65	1.26	1.29	1.94	10.6
sd:	10.2	0.13	0.252	0.0109	2.19

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	281.7	260.7	198.59
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	25.24	18.03	6.02

MAX_MEAN: 50.7 MAX_MED: 52.6 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene

CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20

M4ID: 30005053

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.9	0.987	8
sd:	7.57	0.147	22.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	75.1	1.52	1.7	1.94	18
sd:	31.2	0.254	0.542	0.0144	6.32

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	272.21	272.94	229.24
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	23.89	20.15	10.18

MAX_MEAN: 47.7 MAX_MED: 58.2 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11

M4ID: 30004726

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	106	0.727	2.27
sd:	3.57	0.0314	0.375

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	114	0.768	1.87	2.34	17
sd:	3.84	0.0322	0.262	0.00711	3.33

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	355.23	225.33	218.19
PROB:	0	0.03	0.97
RMSE:	80.64	9.04	7.84

MAX_MEAN: 116 MAX_MED: 118 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 5HPP-33
 CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02
 M4ID: 30004927

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 50.6 0.095 8
 sd: 1.82 0.201 16.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 59.8 0.195 4.3 2.34 1.17
 sd: 2.99 0.137 2.93 0.0633 0.295

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	422.72	298.36	257.04
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	42.85	9.25	5.42

MAX_MEAN: 60.8 MAX_MED: 58.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: SR271425
 CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04
 M4ID: 30005021

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.216 2.79 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 43.1 1.38 7.99 1.73 8.06
 sd: 12.4 0.0727 7.03 0.0367 3.22

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	217.02	223.02	182.4
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	10.6	10.6	4.24

MAX_MEAN: 29.5 MAX_MED: 27 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene

CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20

M4ID: 30005173

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	78.6	1.21	4.73
sd:	3.33	0.0248	0.879

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	87.8	1.24	4.25	2.31	2.77
sd:	6.86	0.0222	0.582	0.0364	0.866

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	327.12	241.34	209.18
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	53.22	14.38	8.16

MAX_MEAN: 100 MAX_MED: 104 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine
 CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15
 M4ID: 30004794

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	142	1.48	2.05
sd:	6.17	0.0346	0.19

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	181	1.64	1.61	2.33	17.8
sd:	30.9	0.144	0.3	0.00518	6.08

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	351.99	218.84	210.99
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	80.98	9.1	7.09

MAX_MEAN: 146 MAX_MED: 148 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Thiabendazole
 CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05
 M4ID: 30004852

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.7	0.875	2
sd:	1.97	0.235	1.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	32.8	1.96	0.687	2.28	17.8
sd:	44.4	1.54	0.389	0.0208	12.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	228.87	199.59	195.9
PROB:	0	0.14	0.86
RMSE:	10.88	6.04	5.17

MAX_MEAN: 17.1 MAX_MED: 21.9 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18

M4ID: 30005223

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	108	0.787	1.43
sd:	4.84	0.0583	0.265

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	161	1.12	0.98	2.4	1.22
sd:	53.6	0.258	0.176	0.197	0.602

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	352.88	244.17	228.42
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	77.97	12.91	9.25

MAX_MEAN: 121 MAX_MED: 119 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene
 CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02
 M4ID: 30004615

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 46 1.91 1.53
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 46 1.77 5.18 3.37 17.9
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	94.74	73.9	68.96
PROB:	0	0.08	0.92
RMSE:	11.1	4.33	2.06

MAX_MEAN: 38.3 MAX_MED: 38.3 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol

CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22

M4ID: 30004955

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	95.2	1.57	1.86
sd:	4.93	0.044	0.177

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	123	1.74	1.53	2.32	11.6
sd:	17.5	0.0959	0.161	0.00714	5.04

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	321.13	206.2	194.43
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	48.81	8.23	6

MAX_MEAN: 90 MAX_MED: 88.1 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30005101

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	46.5	1.66	1.72
sd:	2.2	0.0432	0.171

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	53	1.74	1.62	2.35	17.2
sd:	6.47	0.0834	0.176	0.00795	5.96

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	275.67	153.18	152.15
PROB:	0	0.37	0.63
RMSE:	22.99	2.97	2.75

MAX_MEAN: 41.9 MAX_MED: 42.5 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30005224

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	172	1.11	1.98
sd:	18.7	0.136	1.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	271	1.41	1.12	2.2	3.23
sd:	95.3	0.307	0.503	0.0873	1.29

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.61	334.21	323.14
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	121.77	52.39	41.62

MAX_MEAN: 205 MAX_MED: 197 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2488 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Active_up)

NAME: Benodanil

CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15

M4ID: 30004770

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	57.2	1.52	1.92
sd:	2.75	0.049	0.248

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	69.7	1.64	1.58	2.34	17
sd:	5.94	0.0678	0.152	0.00464	3.27

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	294.39	175.3	158.51
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	31.15	4.16	3.29

MAX_MEAN: 55.8 MAX_MED: 55.4 BMAD: 1.48

COFF: 14.8 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: